

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D5.5

Business Interaction Models for Mission Scale-Up

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The EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030" (hereafter 'Mission Ocean & Waters' or 'the Mission') is a transformative initiative to restore marine and freshwater ecosystems while promoting sustainable economic development. Structured around three key objectives (protecting ecosystems, preventing pollution, and fostering a carbon-neutral blue economy) the Mission seeks to align public and private efforts across the EU. This deliverable, developed under the PREP4BLUE project, explores innovative models for engaging the business community in achieving these objectives, emphasising the need for private sector involvement to ensure sustainable and effective financing.

This report highlights successful interactions between businesses, public entities, and other organisations contributing to the Mission's goals through 12 case studies based on 13 interviews conducted with key stakeholders. The case studies showcase diverse mechanisms for fostering innovation, sustainable growth, and collaboration across Mission Ocean & Waters basins. For each case study, recommendations are outlined for various stakeholders, including businesses, policymakers, academia, and NGOs. These recommendations provide actionable insights for enhancing collaboration and scaling up successful initiatives. While businesses are encouraged to invest in partnerships, leverage funding programmes, and adopt sustainable technologies, policymakers should streamline regulatory processes, promote place-based innovation, and provide incentives for sustainability. Lastly, academia is urged to enhance knowledge transfer and align educational programmes with industry needs, while NGOs are called upon to promote community engagement and support policy advocacy efforts. This report offers a blueprint for fostering deeper collaboration and innovation, ensuring that the blue economy thrives while supporting the long-term health of our ocean and freshwater ecosystems.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and throughout document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
ABT	Atlantic Bluefin Tuna
BaMS	Bioeconomy at Marine Sites
CCMAR	University of Algarve's Centre of Marine Sciences
CLCs	Co-location Centers
CSAs	Mission Ocean Coordination and Support Actions
DGRM	Directorate-General for Natural Resources, Safety and Maritime Services
EIB	European Investment Bank
EIT	European Institute of Innovation & Technology
EMFAF	The European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund
IEO	Spanish Institute of Oceanography
KIC	Knowledge and Innovation Community
KIC WMM	Knowledge and Innovation Community on Water, Marine, and Maritime Sectors and Ecosystems
Mission Ocean/Mission	EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030"
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology
P4B	PREP4BLUE
RAS	Recirculating Aqua System
S3	Smart Specialisation Strategy
SBEP	Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership
SWD	Commission Staff Working Document on a Commission ex-ante analysis on the relevance of a new Knowledge and Innovation Community of the European Institute of Innovation and Technology on Water, Marine and Maritime Sectors and Ecosystems, and confirming its launch in 2016

1 Introduction

The EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030" (hereinafter referred to as "Mission Ocean and Waters" or as "Mission") seeks to establish a comprehensive framework for restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems by 2030. It is structured around three key objectives, each aligned with broader EU policies on sustainability, biodiversity, and the blue economy. These objectives guide the Mission's strategic actions across different sea and freshwater basins, and they serve as the foundation for efforts to protect and restore ecosystems while promoting sustainable economic development. The three primary objectives are:

- **Protect and Restore Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems and Biodiversity.** In line with the [EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030](#), this objective focuses on safeguarding marine and freshwater ecosystems, promoting the restoration of degraded habitats, and enhancing biodiversity by protecting at least 30% and strictly protecting 10% of the EU's marine areas and restoring a minimum of 25,000 km of free-flowing rivers.
- **Prevent and Eliminate Pollution of Our Ocean, Seas, and Waters.** In line with the [EU Action Plan Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water, and Soil](#), Mission Ocean and Waters targets significant reductions in marine and water pollution, including reducing plastic litter at sea by at least 50%, decreasing microplastic pollution by 30%, and cutting nutrient losses and chemical pesticide use by 50%.
- **Make the Sustainable Blue Economy Carbon-Neutral and Circular.** As part of the [European Green Deal](#) and the proposed [European Climate Law](#), this objective focuses on decarbonising maritime activities and promoting circular economic models in the blue economy. By fostering zero-emission and low-impact technologies in industries such as aquaculture and shipping, the Mission aims to transition the blue economy toward carbon neutrality and sustainability by 2030.

Mission Ocean and Waters serves as a catalyst for streamlining and coordinating funding across different levels of government to achieve its ambitious goals.¹ However, for the Mission to fully achieve its goals, it is essential to secure sustainable and sufficient private sector involvement, creating public-private partnerships that can accelerate innovation and scale-up solutions that support both environmental restoration and sustainable economic growth across all Mission basins.

This deliverable (D5.5) aims to explore and propose innovative models for interacting with the business community to support effectively and sustainably finance Mission Ocean and Waters' objectives. The deliverable identifies best practices, successful case studies, and strategic interactions between businesses, public entities, and other stakeholders that contribute to achieving these objectives. This work is part of a broader effort under the PREP4BLUE project to lay the foundation for research and innovation activities critical to Mission Ocean's success.

The primary goal is to examine how and why companies, clusters, EU-wide initiatives, regions, and other entities have aligned their activities with Mission Ocean and Waters' objectives so far while also identifying potential challenges and opportunities for scaling up and replicating these interactions across basins. To this end, this report will present 12 case studies assembled based on findings from 13 interviews conducted with key stakeholders working in different Mission Ocean Basins. The case

¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *EU Missions two years on: assessment of progress and way forward*, Communication, COM(2023) 457, 19 July 2023

studies examine the mechanisms they use to interact either with businesses (or with the private sector, in the case of businesses) and the role these interactions play in advancing Mission Ocean's objectives. The case studies also provide insights and recommendations for fostering further and improved collaboration between businesses, policymakers, academia, and NGOs.

2 Methodology

The primary goal of this deliverable was to identify and analyse innovative approaches for interacting with the business community to effectively support the implementation and sustainable financing of the Mission's objectives. The methodology adopted for this task involved a multi-step process of case study selection, stakeholder engagement, interviews, and desk research to ensure a comprehensive understanding of business models and public-private collaborations aligned with Mission Ocean and Waters.

2.1 Case Study Selection

In collaboration with Prep4Blue's work package five partners, the first step involved carefully selecting relevant case studies. Our focus was on identifying best-case examples from across the Mission Ocean and Waters basins, emphasising interactions between the private sector and public organisations that contribute to the Mission's goals. These examples were chosen based on their proven success in fostering collaboration, sustainable financing, and business commitment to blue economy initiatives. The selected case studies covered a diverse range of actors, including private companies, regional governments, associations, and clusters, all actively working toward Mission Ocean and Waters' objectives.

We also reached out to the Mission Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs) projects to gather additional insights and recommendations on key stakeholders actively engaged in relevant blue economy initiatives. Their input was instrumental in refining our list of case studies to ensure we covered a broad spectrum of examples, both geographically and in terms of sectoral diversity.

2.2 Stakeholder Engagement and Interviews

Once the case studies were selected, we conducted targeted outreach to individuals and organisations closely related to these initiatives, seeking their assistance and availability for a 45-minute interview. These stakeholders included representatives from companies, regional governments, public bodies, associations, clusters, and NGOs who were involved in supporting or participating in Mission Ocean and Waters activities.

After stakeholders had accepted the invitation, they received a detailed interview guide outlining the purpose of the deliverable, the role of their initiative within it, and a set of interview questions (Appendix 1). The interview questions focused on several key areas, such as understanding the motivation behind their involvement, identifying challenges they faced during implementation, and exploring their stakeholder engagement strategies. We also asked about the lessons learned from their experiences and any recommendations they had for replicating their initiatives in other regions or contexts.

A total of 13 interviews were conducted, providing a rich dataset of insights, challenges, and success stories. The discussions were recorded, transcribed, and analysed to extract key insights on each initiative's background, motivation, Mission objectives, interaction type, implementation, and outcomes.

2.3 Desk Research and Compilation of Findings

To supplement the insights gathered through interviews, we conducted additional desk research. This research involved reviewing companies' websites, as well as relevant reports, policy documents, and publicly available resources linked to the case studies. The desk research helped contextualise the interview findings, ensuring that each case study was comprehensive.

The interview and desk research findings were compiled into twelve detailed case studies. Each case study was designed to outline the background of the organisation or company, its motivation in pursuing the initiative, the mechanisms through which it interacts with either the public or the private sector, and the implementation and outcomes of said actions. The case studies also include recommendations for businesses, policymakers, academia, and civil society, providing actionable insights for fostering greater collaboration and support for the Mission.

3 Case Studies

3.1 BlueInvest

3.1.1 Background

BlueInvest is a platform supported by the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFAF), which aims to boost innovation and investment in sustainable technologies for sustainable blue economy. The platform has identified over 500 projects, such as early-stage businesses, SMEs, and scale-ups, seeking to enhance their readiness and supporting them in access to finance. Alongside offering critical network opportunities to meet potential partners and investors, access to pitching and matchmaking events, a knowledge centre and a project pipeline through its online community, BlueInvest supports projects through readiness and fundraising assistance actions. The platform also runs an investor capacity-building programme, offering a dedicated capacity-building track for investors, guiding them to specialise their investment strategies in the blue economy.²

The initiative explores opportunities and innovation across ten key sectors: aquaculture, blue biotechnology, blue renewable energy, blue tech and ocean observation, coastal and maritime tourism, environmental protection and regeneration, fisheries, shipbuilding and refit, shipping and ports, and lastly, water management. Through their [Investor Report](#) publications, the initiative seeks to offer investors an overview of activities and opportunities in the EU blue economy by showcasing key innovative technologies and featuring a sample of investment-ready companies from the BlueInvest pipeline.³ BlueInvest is also supporting the ‘EU Blue Champions’ scheme in collaboration with the European Investment Bank (EIB), an initiative launched in November 2023 dedicated to identifying 20 innovative projects of potential interest to public or private finance providers that could qualify for EIB financing.⁴

The initiative uses dedicated financial instruments like the [InvestEU Blue Economy Fund](#), a risk-sharing financial instrument of 500 million euros dedicated to enhancing the finance ecosystem needed to nurture and scale up new ocean-based technologies and the startups, SMEs, and scale-ups that drive them. Moreover, the initiative also enjoys the support of the EIB’s Advisory Services, namely the [InvestEU Advisory Hub](#), which offers financial and technical expertise to project promoters and local authorities to strengthen projects’ preparation and implementation and to improve the efficient use of EU funds.⁵

3.1.2 Motivation for the Action

Access to finance remains a significant challenge for many SMEs in the blue economy. High-potential yet risky ventures often struggle to secure adequate investment funding. While existing EU support instruments are already addressing large-scale maritime infrastructure and innovation investments, there is a critical need to establish suitable investment vehicles to bridge this gap. For this reason, the European Commission’s efforts on Blue Growth are strongly focusing on blending essential investments from both private and public sources to support the achievement of Mission Ocean and

² https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/ocean/blue-economy/blueinvest_en

³ https://blueinvest-community.converve.io/investor_report.html

⁴ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/news/all-research-and-innovation-news/blue-economy-launch-eu-blue-champions-scheme-support-innovative-projects-helping-restore-ocean-and-2023-11-29_en

⁵ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/news/all-research-and-innovation-news/blue-economy-launch-eu-blue-champions-scheme-support-innovative-projects-helping-restore-ocean-and-2023-11-29_en

Waters objectives. To address this need, BlueInvest was launched to facilitate access to finance and support investment readiness for early-stage businesses, SMEs, and scale-ups in the blue economy.

3.1.3 Mission Objective

By helping blue economy startups and early-stage businesses access finance and become investment-ready, BlueInvest is a critical stakeholder supporting all of Mission Ocean's objectives. The initiative, particularly through the newly launched 'EU Blue Champions' scheme, focuses on supporting 20 technologically and financially mature companies that have the potential to contribute to one or more of the Mission's objectives to a significant extent. The first 20 winners were unveiled in May 2024 by the European Commission and the EIB, the list including companies working in a variety of sectors ranging from tidal and wind energy solutions, underwater robotics, and vertical research vessels to satellite data applications for blue technologies, and aquaculture or biorefinery activities.⁶ For instance, French company Inalve was awarded the title in light of its efforts to revolutionise microalgae cultivation by developing a patented method that optimises the use of natural resources while minimising ecological impact, contributing to decarbonising the blue economy. Similarly, the Greek company SciDrones IKE, a spin-off company of the University of the Aegean specialising in the development and deployment of advanced machine learning algorithms for scientific research and environmental monitoring, received the award for its marine litter pollution monitoring on coastal zones. Lastly, companies like WSense, an Italian scale-up specialising in underwater wireless communication and monitoring systems, seek to contribute to restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity through innovative technology that can enable real-time, continuous monitoring and data transmission from underwater environments.

3.1.4 Interaction Type

Blue Invest is a public sector initiative started by the European Commission and enabled by EMFAF. The day-to-day operations, as well as the investor's reporting are managed by a contractor, PwC Luxembourg. Given its goal to support early-stage businesses, SMEs, and scale-ups in the blue economy, the initiative is highly involved with the private sector. Companies that have used support instruments provided by the initiative have credited PwC's private sector knowledge for BlueInvest's successful engagement with companies and investors.

Moreover, investor partners of the initiative, like the [Swen Partners' Blue Ocean Fund](#), play a crucial role in bridging the gap between innovative startups and necessary funding. Swen Partners operates by raising funds from asset owners such as insurers, banks, and pension funds. They then developed a strategy to invest in alignment with the goals of the Blue Ocean Fund. This fund, managed by Swen Partners in a scientific partnership with [Ifremer](#), focuses on regenerating ocean biodiversity by addressing key threats such as overfishing, ocean pollution, and climate change. By closely collaborating with BlueInvest, investors like Swen Partners gain access to a pipeline of investment-ready projects nurtured and supported through BlueInvest's readiness and fundraising assistance programmes. This collaboration has facilitated investments in several promising startups that have graduated from BlueInvest's investor readiness programmes. In addition, through the Blue Ocean Fund, Swen Partners have already started to support 'EU Blue Champions' companies, like [ECOsubsea](#),

⁶ <https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2021-161-the-european-commission-and-european-investment-bank-group-join-forces-to-protect-the-oceans-and-boost-investment-in-the-sustainable-blue-economy?recommendation=1>

a Norwegian company that develops robotic shell cleaning technology for environmentally friendly underwater hull cleaning of vessels while in port.⁷

3.1.5 Implementation

3.1.5.1 BlueInvest Community

The [BlueInvest Community](#) is an online platform that connects entrepreneurs, investors, corporate and innovation stakeholders operating in the Blue Economy. The platform offers opportunities to network with projects, startups or SMEs, investors, stakeholders, coaches, and mid-cap or large corporations, presents BlueInvest events, and grants access to the BlueInvest Pipeline Dashboard and Knowledge Centre.

3.1.5.1.1 BlueInvest Project Pipeline

The BlueInvest Project Pipeline showcases innovative and scalable business ventures from traditional and emerging sectors of the maritime economy, innovative projects, and entrepreneurs working to shape the blue economy.

3.1.5.1.2 BlueInvest Events

BlueInvest events feature learning opportunities, knowledge exchange, networking and B2B matchmaking in formats designed to support business. Examples of events include Thematic Workshops dedicated to each of the Blue Economy sectors analysed by BlueInvest, investor workshops, e-pitching sessions, webinars dedicated to each EU basin and other Webinars.

3.1.5.1.3 BlueInvest Academy

The BlueInvest Digital Academy, open to members of the BlueInvest Community, offers capacity-building courses, training events and exclusive webinars to accelerate business for investment, market access and international expansion. Features include seminars on the latest industry developments and trends, sessions with market experts, talks and speed mentoring to help you with your go-to-market approach.

3.1.5.2 BlueInvest Readiness Assistance

BlueInvest Readiness Assistance is a coaching programme offered to high-potential startups and SMEs with innovative and sustainable products and solutions for the Blue Economy. Businesses and projects selected for Investment Readiness Assistance receive coaching packages tailored specifically to their readiness levels and business objectives. The programme provides business support to help startups and SMEs build capacities for growth and attract investment.

3.1.6 Outcomes

Successful Fundraising and Scaling

Through BlueInvest's support, companies like [Inalve](#), a Blue Champion in aquaculture, have successfully raised funds and scaled their operations. Inalve has developed a pilot farm, showcasing its ability to attract investment and expand its sustainable aquaculture practices.

Technological Advancements and Market Readiness

⁷ <https://www.meretmarine.com/fr/marine-marchande/biofouling-le-fonds-francais-blue-ocean-investit-dans-l-operateur-de-robots-ecosubsea>

Wsense, an Italian company specialising in ocean tech, has made significant strides in developing underwater telecommunication technology. This technology, which has dual-use potential for both commercial and defence purposes, exemplifies the market readiness and innovation that BlueInvest promotes. Wsense's advancements in ocean tech highlight the successful translation of research into practical applications.

Public Sector Contracts and Revenue Generation

[Promethee Earth Intelligence](#) has secured contracts with the public sector, providing a stable revenue stream necessary for scaling up. These contracts demonstrate how BlueInvest's initiatives help companies navigate and leverage public sector opportunities, resulting in tangible financial benefits and growth.

Environmental Impact through Pollution Reduction

[Ecosubsea](#) in Norway has achieved concrete outcomes in reducing marine pollution. By providing cleaning services for ports and vessels, Ecosubsea addresses biofouling and helps maintain cleaner marine environments. This outcome directly aligns with Mission Ocean's objective of reducing pollution and showcases the environmental impact of BlueInvest-supported projects.

Renewable Energy Production

[EnerOcean's](#) project in Spain, which involves installing a wind energy platform in the Canary Islands, aims to increase renewable energy production. Although the project's success is contingent on receiving timely permits from the public sector, the potential outcome is a significant increase in Spain's renewable energy capacity. This project highlights the alignment of BlueInvest's initiatives with sustainable energy goals.

Development of Innovation Hubs

[Innovamare](#) in Croatia, another recipient of BlueInvest's Blue Champions award⁸, has developed an innovation lab focused on underwater robotics and ocean observation. Supported by grants from the Croatian government and the EU, Innovamare has created a hub for technological testing and development. This innovation hub not only advances marine technology but also generates jobs and added value in the region, showcasing the socio-economic outcomes of BlueInvest's initiatives.

3.1.7 Recommendations

3.1.7.1 For Businesses

Start-ups and SMEs should focus on improving their ability to articulate the business value of their solutions. This includes better preparation for investor pitches and understanding how to present their innovations effectively to potential clients. As observed by BlueInvest, many startups have great ideas but lack the business skills to convince investors. Businesses should aim to secure significant public sector contracts, which can provide stable revenue streams and make them more attractive to investors.

3.1.7.2 For Policymakers

Policymakers should work on simplifying the procurement processes and reducing the time required to secure public contracts. The current complexity and length of these processes are major barriers to

⁸ <https://mairos.org/conference/blue-champion-award-press-conference/>

business growth. A representative from BlueInvest highlighted the need for more straightforward and faster procurement procedures.

Implementing regulations that allow for a smooth transition rather than immediate drastic changes can help businesses adapt and grow. Policymakers should consider the impact of regulations on businesses and provide the necessary support to help them comply without stifling their growth.

Encouraging and supporting public-private partnerships can create environments that foster innovation and growth. Examples like Innovamare show how such collaborations can develop innovation hubs and drive technological advancements.

3.1.7.3 For NGOs and Civil Society

NGOs and civil society organisations should work to raise awareness about the opportunities in the sustainable blue economy and foster collaboration between different stakeholders. This includes highlighting successful case studies and facilitating knowledge exchange between businesses, the public sector, and research institutions.

3.1.7.4 For Academia

Universities should focus on better integrating research with business applications. Supporting technological transfer and helping researchers understand the commercial potential of their innovations can drive more impactful projects. BlueInvest also emphasised the need for universities to develop innovations with clear business value.

Educational institutions should ensure that their programmes are aligned with the skills needed in the sustainable blue economy. This includes fostering business partnerships to understand their requirements and developing curricula that prepare students for these roles. Addressing skill shortages through targeted education can help startups and SMEs hire competent people and grow.

3.2 Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership

3.2.1 Background

The [Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership](#) (SBEP) and [Innovation Norway](#) are working together to support the advancement of sustainable practices and fostering innovation in the blue economy sector. The SBEP, a collaborative initiative, focuses on promoting ocean restoration, pollution prevention, and the development of a circular and sustainable blue economy. As part of these goals, transnational calls for proposals are carried out on the priority areas of the strategic research and innovation agenda. The partnership aims to support projects that contribute to these objectives, also by providing them access to critical support packages. In fulfilling this objective, the support and experience of Innovation Norway is particularly critical, as the organisation has extensive experience in supporting Norwegian startups accessing programmes such as the EIB Accelerator.

The first kick-offs for the first projects funded under the SBEP are scheduled for September 2024 in Madrid. The partnership's strategic efforts include integrating market and business readiness considerations from the outset of project planning. This approach aims to bridge the gap between technological innovation and market uptake, ensuring that projects are not only scientifically sound but also commercially viable. Overall, the SBEP and Innovation Norway collaborate to foster innovation and sustainable practices in the blue economy, addressing critical challenges such as ocean restoration, pollution reduction, and the transition to a circular economy. Their work includes providing financial support, enhancing business readiness, and facilitating partnerships between public and private sectors, aiming to create a thriving and sustainable blue economy in Norway and beyond.

3.2.2 Motivation for the Action

The SBEP is driven by the need to foster innovation in the blue economy to address environmental challenges while supporting economic development. The SBEP's core motivation is to align research and innovation efforts across Europe to address the dual challenges of ocean sustainability and economic competitiveness. The partnership focuses on leveraging Europe's collective knowledge, technological capabilities, and resources to generate impactful solutions that support marine ecosystem health, reduce pollution, and promote circular and climate-neutral economic activities within the blue economy.⁹ Moreover, SBEP is motivated by a need to enhance collaboration between academia, industry, and public stakeholders to ensure that solutions developed have both scientific rigour and market viability, both critical assets for their long-term financial sustainability.

3.2.3 Mission Objective

The SBEP is closely aligned with the European Green Deal, the Biodiversity Strategy, and Mission Ocean and Waters. The partnership's mission is to build a climate-neutral, sustainable, productive and competitive blue economy by 2030 and to create good conditions for a healthy ocean by 2050. To achieve this, SBEP aims to stimulate the creation of new technologies, products, and practices that enhance the resilience of marine ecosystems while contributing to a sustainable and inclusive economy. Through its projects, SBEP seeks to help Europe achieve climate neutrality in the maritime

⁹ https://bluepartnership.eu/sites/bluepartnership.eu/files/documents/2023-07/Sustainable%20Blue%20Economy%20Partnership%20draft%20SRIA_V1.0.1_0.pdf

sector by 2050, foster the restoration of marine biodiversity, and ensure that economic growth in blue sectors is aligned with ecological sustainability.

3.2.4 Interaction Type

The SBEP facilitates extensive collaboration between public and private sectors, academia, and NGOs. As a co-funded partnership, it is financed by Horizon Europe funding and engages 74 Partner institutions from 29 countries, as well as the European Commission, to pool research and innovation investments and align national programmes at a pan-European scale. The partnership is coordinated by the Italian Ministry of Universities and Research and co-coordinated by the Research Council of Norway.¹⁰

The partnership's thematic workshops, matchmaking events, and public procurement processes are going to be structured in partnership with Innovation Norway to provide a productive platform for industry-academia collaboration and seek to ensure that emerging solutions are market-ready. Innovation Norway is the Norwegian government's funding agency that provides loans, grants, and guarantees to Norwegian companies and serves as Norway's official trade representative abroad.¹¹ Annually, it allocates between 700 to 800 million euros to support various industries, including those within the blue economy. The organisation is also responsible for mobilising Norwegian companies to participate in the [European Innovation Council \(EIC\) Accelerator](#) under the Horizon Europe programme, helping companies develop technologies and scale up to enter European markets. Hence, they have extensive experience supporting startups and SMEs, offering them comprehensive support packages, including thematic workshops, application assistance, and pitching training, to enhance the companies' chances of success. This experience is of particular value to SBEP, as it seeks to support its projects in becoming successful market-ready solutions.

3.2.5 Implementation

The SBEP has adopted a collaborative and integrated approach to implementing its projects. Through joint calls for proposals and co-funding mechanisms, the partnership supports research and innovation projects that address key challenges in the blue economy, such as marine pollution, sustainable aquaculture, and ocean restoration. The partnership also emphasises capacity building, focusing on developing human capital through training, mobility schemes, and promoting ocean literacy. By integrating scientific research with practical, industry-driven initiatives, SBEP is keen to ensure that its projects have a tangible impact on marine ecosystem restoration and sustainable economic practices and result in the creation of successful products ready for market uptake. One of the key aspects of its implementation ambition is ensuring projects are tailored to the specific needs of the regional sea basins and are scalable across different geographic contexts. This is closely tied to the pan-European alignment of research and innovation priorities, which involves cooperation across sea basins, enabling projects to adapt to local contexts while being scalable to broader regions.¹²

3.2.6 Outcomes

SBEP's outcomes are expected to contribute to a thriving blue economy that is both ecologically sustainable and economically viable. The partnership's projects will generate new technologies and best practices that reduce the environmental impact of blue economy activities while promoting the

¹⁰ <https://www.jpi-oceans.eu/en/sustainable-blue-economy-partnership>

¹¹ <https://en.innovasjon Norge.no/article/our-mission>

¹² https://bluepartnership.eu/sites/bluepartnership.eu/files/documents/2023-07/Sustainable%20Blue%20Economy%20Partnership%20draft%20SRIA_V1.0.1_0.pdf

sustainable use of marine resources. Additionally, SBEP has the ambition to deliver important policy inputs and feedback in order to foster a better alignment between marine environmental goals and economic activities. By 2030, the partnership aims to significantly improve the health of European seas and oceans, restore marine biodiversity, and support the transition to a climate-neutral blue economy through the widespread adoption of innovative technologies and solutions. SBEP's outcomes will also include strengthened transnational cooperation in the marine and maritime sectors, better alignment of research priorities across the EU, and enhanced public engagement through ocean literacy initiatives.

3.2.7 Recommendations

3.2.7.1 For Businesses

Startups and SMEs in the blue economy sector should consult and engage with the opportunities created by SBEP. The partnership can offer these businesses the chance to collaborate with research institutions and benefit from funding for innovation and sustainability. By accessing the support of the SBEP, at the end of their journey with SBEP, they can explore funding opportunities provided by initiatives like the EIC Accelerator, which provides both grants and equity to help companies scale their innovations to European markets. Moreover, as the SBEP seeks to replicate the successful model of Innovation Norway, companies would be able to take advantage of thematic workshops and pitch training sessions.

Moreover, SBEP stressed how startups and SMEs that seek to operate within the blue economy sector should prioritise developing and adopting sustainable technologies and practices that align with long-term environmental goals. Moreover, Innovation Norway's experience underscores that businesses need to understand that market readiness and business model alignment with EU priorities are essential for growth and success in the evolving regulatory landscape. Furthermore, engaging in partnerships with public bodies, research institutions, and private investors through collaborative projects can help businesses access funding and create innovative solutions that are both scalable and profitable.

3.2.7.2 For Policymakers

Policymakers should ensure that frameworks for financial support are in place to help maritime and ocean-related businesses overcome the capital gap that hinders investment in green technologies. As emphasised by Innovation Norway, there is a notable gap in funding for large-scale, sustainable blue economy projects, and even countries like Norway face challenges in providing substantial capital. European Union programmes, such as the EIC Accelerator, can serve as models for creating grant and equity-based funding to help address this gap and stimulate innovation in the blue economy. Additionally, policies should focus on ensuring that integrating environmental goals with economic activities is feasible by promoting public-private partnerships and facilitating access to international markets.

3.2.7.3 For Academia

Academic institutions should strengthen their role as key contributors to the blue economy innovation pipeline by fostering interdisciplinary research and collaborating with businesses on applied research that addresses market demands. There is a significant need for academia to upskill human resources, as emphasised in the SBEP's strategic agenda. Universities should develop programmes and partnerships that support knowledge transfer between research and industry, emphasising hands-on training and mobility programmes.

3.3 KIC Water, Marine and Maritime Sectors and Ecosystems

3.3.1 Background

The Knowledge and Innovation Community (KIC) of the [European Institute of Innovation and Technology \(EIT\)](#) on Water, Marine and Maritime sectors and ecosystems (KIC WMM) is an upcoming Horizon Europe scheme relevant to the Mission's stakeholders. The project, set to launch in 2026, involves the creation of an independent entity (company) by a consortium of 50 stakeholders¹³ from the so-called "Knowledge Triangle"¹⁴, hence gathering Education, Business Creation, and Innovation stakeholders, such as research centres, companies, universities, innovation clusters and more. During its first years of operation, funding is envisioned to originate from the Horizon Europe budget (via EIT) and decrease gradually over a maximum period of 15 years to allow the entity to achieve financial sustainability. The annual subsidy to KIC WMM is expected to entail approximately 30 million euros to fund services, programmes, and projects for the whole KIC WMM ecosystem beyond the consortium members through opportunities such as open calls for proposals or challenges for startups.

Nine KICs have been established since 2008, working on nine different challenges (Figure 1).¹⁵ While these are twin organisations with similar characteristics, their specific structure differs, as they are independent entities. However, all of them support the implementation of training activities and research projects with commercial potential, as well as startups at several stages of the entrepreneurial process, financially and immaterially (through mentoring and training). Every KIC has one headquarters and several regional offices called Co-location Centres (CLCs) that oversee nurturing their regional innovation ecosystem. Some of the already functioning KICs tackle topics related to Mission Ocean, as water and the ocean relate to numerous sectors by nature, for example, [EIT InnoEnergy](#) and [EIT Food](#).

¹³ 50 at the launch, and more are to be included throughout the process.

¹⁴ <https://www.eitmanufacturing.eu/what-we-do/the-eit-knowledge-triangle/>

¹⁵ These include added value manufacturing ([EIT Manufacturing](#)), climate change ([EIT Climate-KIC](#)), cultural and creative sectors and industries ([EIT Culture & Creativity](#)), Digitalisation ([EIT Digital](#)), future of food ([EIT Food](#)), health innovation ([EIT Health](#)), raw materials ([EIT RawMaterials](#)), Sustainable Energy ([EIT InnoEnergy](#)), and urban mobility ([EIT Urban Mobility](#)).

Figure 1. Overview of eight of the existing nine KICs

(Source: <https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/the-european-institute-of-innovation-technology-eit/>)

3.3.2 Motivation for the Action

EIT was created in 2008 during the last months of the 2007/2008 financial crisis and is part of the European Union Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under the Pillar “Innovative Europe”. Europe is in an excellent position to seize opportunities arising from the most important challenges the continent faces thanks to its wealth of leading universities, companies, and research organisations, as well as a highly educated and skilled workforce and innovative startups. However, turning this solid foundation of organisations and talent into tangible solutions for global societal challenges requires a specific approach to innovation that emphasises mutual inspiration and new collaboration methods toward shared goals. In this context, EIT plays a crucial role.

KICs are independent entities created as integrated partnerships, working on implementing concrete activities on the ground alongside various relevant stakeholders. A KIC is “an integrated partnership, operating within the EIT Community, at the core of which are research organisations, educational institutions, businesses (including SMEs) and other innovation stakeholders such as public authorities or non-governmental organisations, united by the focus on a major global challenge”.¹⁶ At present, nine KICs exist, focusing on nine challenges (Figure 1), with the challenge of water, marine and maritime sectors and ecosystems and KIC WMM being next in line. In fact, EIT regularly launches open calls to foster the creation of new KICs and guides the existing ones, monitoring their operation,

¹⁶ EIT Innovation Model Publication, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2021 - <https://eit.europa.eu/library/eit-innovation-model-publication>

releasing funding and fostering collaboration among different KICs on common areas of interest (e.g., [Innovation Capacity Building for Higher Education Initiative](#), [Deep Tech Talent Initiative](#), [Girls Go Circular](#), etc.).¹⁷ In much the same way that EIT was born out of the need to address global economic challenges post-2008, the KIC WMM emerges as a solution to today's urgent environmental crises. It will foster resilient and adaptive solutions for water and marine ecosystems, just as the previous KICs did for other sectors.

3.3.3 Mission Objectives

The KIC WMM aligns with all three of Mission Ocean and Waters' core objectives: protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, preventing and eliminating pollution, and creating a carbon-neutral and circular blue economy. The most recent Commission Staff Working Document on the launch of KIC WMM (SWD)¹⁸ specifies the initiative's scope, building upon two legal sources: the [EIT Regulation](#)¹⁹ and the [EIT Strategic Innovation Agenda \(SIA\) 2021-2027](#).²⁰ Three main challenges are identified: water scarcity, ecosystem degradation, and establishing a circular and sustainable blue economy.

The winning consortium will determine the specific topics the KIC WMM will address within these three challenges, ensuring that the selected focus areas are the most relevant to current environmental and socio-economic needs. Nonetheless, the SWD suggests that the KIC WMM should focus on topics that bridge freshwater and marine ecosystems, ensuring interdisciplinary solutions that span sectors like sensor technologies, ecosystem restoration, biotechnologies, and food production (agriculture, aquaculture, fisheries). This cross-sectoral approach aligns with EIT's philosophy and is envisioned to promote synergies that address complex environmental challenges with innovative, scalable solutions.

Ecosystem restoration, particularly the land-sea continuum, is central to KIC WMM's mission. Projects will aim to reverse ecosystem degradation while addressing pollution challenges such as plastics, chemicals, and noise pollution. Additionally, the KIC will contribute to developing advanced monitoring and forecasting tools to enhance ecological responses. Finally, by recognising the economic value of marine and freshwater ecosystems, KIC WMM will ensure that ecosystem services are integrated into sustainable business models. Through cross-sector collaboration and innovative projects, KIC WMM will play a critical role in achieving Mission Ocean's objectives.

3.3.4 Interaction Type

Similarly to the other EIT KICs, KIC WMM will implement different mechanisms (direct funding, start-up support, and other initiatives) to support the whole innovation ecosystem in the [Knowledge Triangle](#) and develop solutions to ocean and water challenges. The Knowledge Triangle is a strategic framework that connects research, education, and innovation, aiming to create a synergistic relationship among these critical areas. This model is particularly emphasised by EIT, which leverages

¹⁷ <https://www.eitmanufacturing.eu/what-we-do/cross-kic-transversal-activities/>

¹⁸ The document is titled "Commission Staff Working Document on a Commission ex-ante analysis on the relevance of a new Knowledge and Innovation Community of the European Institute of Innovation and Technology on Water, Marine and Maritime Sectors and Ecosystems, and confirming its launch in 2016" (SWD) <https://education.ec.europa.eu/news/new-eit-knowledge-and-innovation-community-will-focus-on-water-marine-and-maritime-sectors-and-ecosystems>

¹⁹ Regulation (EU) 2021/819 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 on the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (recast) PE/8/2021/REV/1 (OJ L 189, 28.5.2021, p. 61–90), <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2021/819/oj>

²⁰ Decision (EU) 2021/820 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 on the Strategic Innovation Agenda of the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) 2021-2027: Boosting the Innovation Talent and Capacity of Europe and repealing Decision No 1312/2013/EU, PE/9/2021/REV/1 (OJ L 189, 28.5.2021, p. 91–118), <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dec/2021/820/oj>

the model to foster collaboration between academia, industry, and research institutions, intending to drive innovation and economic growth and address societal challenges.²¹ As KICs also leverage the same paradigm in their projects, KIC WMM will not only engage but also actively work to connect stakeholders from research and education with those working on business solutions from the private sector.

3.3.5 Implementation

As mentioned, KICs serve as collaborative platforms for research, education, and industry stakeholders to share knowledge and co-create solutions. These communities are designed to speed up the transfer of research findings into educational programmes and innovative products, thereby ensuring that Europe remains competitive on the global stage. In practice, the Knowledge Triangle creates a continuous feedback loop: research informs education, which shapes future research agendas, and both are translated into innovative products and services. KICs embody this principle by supporting entrepreneurship, developing innovative educational programmes, and fostering partnerships across sectors.

Through the Knowledge Triangle, the EIT and KICs aim to bridge the gap between research and the market, transforming scientific knowledge into tangible societal benefits. This model enhances the impact of research and education while ensuring that both scientific excellence and practical needs drive innovation. It creates a dynamic ecosystem where knowledge is constantly generated, disseminated, and applied. KIC WMM will ensure that the specific challenges of the water, marine, and maritime sectors are met.

EIT Food - Sustainable Aquaculture Competition

The [EIT Food's Sustainable Aquaculture Competition](#), initiated in December 2020, was a significant part of a broader effort to promote sustainability within the aquaculture sector. This competition was designed to bolster the innovation portfolio of EIT Food's 2021-2023 Business Plan while attracting new partners dedicated to transforming aquaculture into a more sustainable method of food production. The competition drew participation from 85 organisations, resulting in 32 project proposals. Out of these, seven projects were selected as winners, each addressing critical challenges in the aquaculture industry. These challenges include reducing food loss and waste, improving fish welfare and disease prevention, developing sustainable fish feeds, and preserving marine biodiversity.

Among the standout projects was the creation of a sustainable fish feed derived from recycled wastewater, which seeks to replace traditional fishmeal and soy-based feeds.²² The NextTuna startup, which was also highlighted in another case study in this report (see section 3.43.4), was also a standout project from the event. Both projects are closely aligned with the EU's [Farm to Fork Strategy](#) and the [European Green Deal](#), which underscore the need for sustainable food systems as key to combating climate change and preserving ecosystems. In addition to fostering innovation, the competition successfully brought 18 new partners into the EIT Food community, highlighting a robust collaborative effort to promote sustainable practices in aquaculture. These initiatives represent crucial steps toward achieving a circular economy in food production and strengthening the resilience of Europe's aquaculture sector. This scheme is both about funding collaborative research and innovation projects and directly supporting startups.

²¹ <https://eit.europa.eu/library/catalysing-innovation-knowledge-triangle-practices-eit-knowledge-and-innovation-communities>

²² This is the 'Ground-breaking Circular Economy Feed Ingredient for Farmed Salmon' EIT Food project, led by Cewatech (<https://www.eitfood.eu/blog/fish-feed-why-we-need-sustainable-alternatives>)

EIT Food - AGAPE

Another significant initiative carried out by EIT Food is closely related to education. In 2021, EIT Food began to support [AGAPE, the Aquacultural Global AI Platform for Europe's Skills Passport](#), an AI-based collaborative platform, as part of the above-mentioned Sustainable Aquaculture Competition.²³ The platform addresses the EU aquaculture market, academia, consumers and research ecosystems and brings an innovative interaction model between stakeholders. It focuses on promoting the transition from the ordinary aquaculture market to a circular economy approach in the aquaculture field on re-skilling processes and awareness of cross-knowledge. It is supposed to broaden the community on skills, capabilities and competencies globally and in real-time, answering effective market demand for competencies. AGAPE represents an opportunity to contribute to a real transition towards a new, sustainable, human-centred aquaculture ecosystem.

EIT Climate-KIC – Collaboration with Open Ocean (Sinay)

Through programmes like the [ClimAccelerator](#), EIT Climate-KIC seeks to equip startups with the tools and resources needed to scale their solutions and attract investment, contributing to systemic changes essential for addressing climate challenges. In supporting startups working on climate innovation, [EIT Climate-KIC](#) has also directly supported the start-up [Open Ocean](#) (now [Sinay](#))²⁴, based on their mutual dedication to promoting climate innovation and adaptation, particularly within the blue economy. Open Ocean (Sinay), recognised for its expertise in oceanographic data and analytics, aligns with EIT Climate-KIC's objectives as it seeks to enhance climate resilience in marine and coastal ecosystems through advanced data-driven insights and technological solutions. EIT Climate-KIC support includes providing access to specialised knowledge, mentorship, and networking opportunities. Through the ClimAccelerator, EIT Climate-KIC is actively harnessing innovation to bolster climate adaptation and resilience, also in critical sectors like marine environments.

EIT InnoEnergy – Co-Investment Support

[EIT InnoEnergy](#) plays a crucial role in accelerating and scaling up innovations in the sustainable energy sector, aligning closely with Mission Ocean and Waters' objectives of fostering a circular and sustainable blue economy. InnoEnergy's approach to supporting innovation goes beyond traditional funding by co-investing in promising companies and offering extensive business support to help them grow. In 2023, EIT InnoEnergy successfully raised over EUR 140 million in a private placement round, attracting new strategic investors such as Societe Generale, Santander CIB, Renault Group, and others.²⁵ These funds will be used to increase the deal flow of early-stage innovative technologies, especially in capital-intensive sectors like clean technology, which require significant initial investment but hold high potential for long-term sustainability.

InnoEnergy's model is designed to de-risk and accelerate the global expansion of startups by leveraging its unique ecosystem of over 1,200 partners, including industrial players, investors, research centres, and public administrations. This ecosystem provides startups with a "one-stop shop" to access funding, mentorship, and industrial scale-up opportunities. Since its inception in 2010, InnoEnergy has supported 200 companies, including three unicorns, and has raised over EUR 9.7 billion in investments. Its portfolio companies are on track to generate EUR 110 billion in revenue and save 2.1 gigatonnes of CO₂e by 2030, demonstrating a substantial contribution to global climate goals. By co-investing and guiding these companies through their growth phases, InnoEnergy not only

²³ <https://www.eitfood.eu/news/eit-food-announces-new-projects-to-accelerate-innovation-in-sustainable-aquaculture>

²⁴ <https://www.climate-kic.org/start-ups/open-ocean/>

²⁵ <https://eit.europa.eu/news-events/news/eit-innoenergy-secures-over-eur-140-million-private-placement-round>

supports their financial sustainability but also ensures they contribute to broader European objectives, such as the Green Deal and the 2050 net-zero target. This co-investment strategy serves as a model for KIC WMM, showing how strategic investments and ecosystem support can accelerate innovation in the blue economy, making it both financially and environmentally sustainable.

Lessons for KIC WMM (Water, Marine and Maritime Sectors and Ecosystems) from Existing KIC Initiatives

The initiatives from other KICs, such as EIT Food's Sustainable Aquaculture Competition, ClimAccelerator, and EIT InnoEnergy, offer valuable insights for KIC WMM. These examples highlight the importance of cross-sectoral collaboration, tailored support for startups, and strategic co-investment. KIC WMM can build on these models by fostering interdisciplinary partnerships to address complex challenges in the blue economy, offering tailored support to startups developing water and marine technologies, and using strategic funding mechanisms to scale impactful solutions.

Moreover, by focusing on market-oriented innovations, KIC WMM can ensure that research translates into real-world applications, contributing to the sustainable growth of the blue economy while addressing Mission Ocean and Waters' goals of ecosystem restoration, pollution reduction, and circular economy practices. Leveraging lessons from existing KICs, KIC WMM can accelerate innovation and create long-term solutions for water, marine, and maritime sectors.

3.3.6 Recommendations

3.3.6.1 For Businesses

Businesses, especially startups and SMEs, should actively invest in sustainable practices and technologies. By partnering with a KIC, they can access a community committed to supporting innovation and collaboration across stakeholders, which is crucial for success. Startups and SMEs are encouraged to apply to KIC calls to run collaborative projects with research institutions, NGOs, and academia, which can accelerate innovation, provide strategic support, and attract investment.

For large companies, partnering with a KIC means becoming a shareholder or a first-level partner, which means having access to the governing bodies of these entities. This can be helpful for networking and promoting the company's priorities. Being part of a KIC also gives companies access to new, innovative ideas from the whole community, for example, startups with solutions to a challenge they may be facing or ideas they find worth investing in.

3.3.6.2 For Policymakers

Place-based innovation plays a crucial role in the success of EIT and the KICs. Through their regional hubs, known as CLCs, KICs engage directly with their macro-regions, fostering strong ties between research centres, innovation ecosystems, and regional institutions. This collaboration is key to supporting the innovation process and advancing the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of new technologies, thereby accelerating their commercialisation. By promoting technological advancement, KICs help companies increase their TRL, making the regions where these companies operate more innovative and competitive.

Given this regional focus, policymakers must support KIC actions through S3/S4 strategies, ensuring alignment with regional priorities. The Mission Ocean and Waters, and the KIC WMM should also join forces at the regional level, leveraging these place-based innovation ecosystems to drive sustainable solutions for the blue economy.

Academic institutions should focus on research that promotes sustainable practices and innovations. By leveraging KIC funding, academia can not only advance technological solutions but also develop educational resources that support public awareness and sustainable initiatives. Partnering with industry players allows for the translation of academic research into practical applications that can benefit society and the environment.

In line with the Knowledge Triangle approach, universities and research institutions can collaborate with startups and large companies to achieve a shared goal of societal impact. Initiatives such as AGAPE, the AI-based collaborative platform supported by EIT Food, can serve as models for fostering skills and competencies in sustainable aquaculture and the blue economy, ensuring that the workforce is well-prepared for future innovations. Public education and outreach are also key for academia to help align stakeholders and the public with the goals of sustainable development and Mission Ocean objectives.

3.3.6.4 For NGOs and Civil Society

NGOs and civil society groups play a critical role in advocating for sustainable practices and policies that support Mission Ocean and Waters' objectives. These organisations should focus on engaging local communities in sustainable initiatives, ensuring that the public is aware of the environmental challenges and the importance of sustainable practices. By translating complex scientific data into accessible information, NGOs can help build community awareness and participation in efforts to protect marine and freshwater ecosystems. NGOs should also seek partnerships with businesses, academia, and policymakers to leverage expertise and resources. Collaboration across these sectors ensures that sustainable solutions are developed with broad support, helping to amplify their impact. Advocacy for supportive policies, including those that promote circular economy principles and carbon-neutral practices, is crucial to creating long-term, systemic change.

3.4 NextTuna

3.4.1 Background

[NextTuna](#), NextTuna, a Germany-based company founded in 2020, is addressing the challenge of meeting the growing global demand for Atlantic Bluefin Tuna (ABT) through sustainable aquaculture. Tuna farming, particularly ABT, has not yet reached commercial-scale reproduction, and NextTuna is pioneering a solution by closing the reproduction cycle of ABT in captivity, an innovation crucial to preserving wild stocks and ensuring the species' future. The company aims to revolutionise the tuna industry by introducing commercial-scale, sustainable tuna farming.

In 2023, NextTuna benefited from the BlueInvest Fundraising Assistance Programme, which provided essential support for scaling its operations, and won the BlueInvest Award 2023 in the category "Sustainable Food and Feed from the Ocean".²⁶ Additionally, NextTuna was a standout project from the EIT Food's Sustainable Aquaculture Competition, initiated in December 2020 as part of a broader effort to promote sustainability within the aquaculture sector. This competition attracted 85 organisations and led to several groundbreaking innovations, including NextTuna's efforts to close the life cycle of ABT reproduction in captivity.

The company collaborates closely with partners like the Spanish Institute of Oceanography (IEO). In 2023, their partner achieved a global first by successfully spawning ABT in a land-based recirculating aqua system (RAS). This closed-loop water system allows for controlled and optimal conditions for tuna breeding, laying the groundwork for scaling up operations to commercial levels. Additionally, NextTuna is advancing the development of the Floating RAS-X system, a cutting-edge technology that merges the best aspects of land-based RAS with the flexibility of a floating platform. This system, designed to be cost-effective, environmentally friendly, and scalable, is expected to go into operation in Spain in 2024. NextTuna aims to grow ABT up to a weight of 10 kilograms in their facilities before transferring them to other farms where the tuna will be raised to market weight. This approach will significantly reduce the reliance on wild-caught tuna for farming purposes, advancing the sustainability of the global tuna industry.²⁷

3.4.2 Motivation for the Action

NextTuna is driven by the urgent need to address the unsustainable demand for wild-caught ABT while advancing innovative aquaculture technologies. ABT populations have been under pressure due to overfishing, and the company sees an opportunity to play a significant role in ensuring the species' future through sustainable farming. Andrew Eckhardt, one of the co-founders, noted that achieving commercial-scale reproduction of ABT could not only safeguard the species but also revive the European tuna industry. Thereby, the company's mission is to provide a sustainable source of ABT that meets growing consumer demand while reducing the environmental impact of traditional fishing methods. Nonetheless, their ambition extends beyond commercial success. NextTuna's work is focused on reducing biological risks, optimising its infrastructure, and ensuring long-term sustainability. The company's three-phase plan includes risk reduction, infrastructure development, and expanding its operations globally, positioning it as a key player in the future of sustainable tuna farming.²⁸

²⁶ https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/news/bluefins-blueinvest-next-tunas-sustainable-solution-2024-03-04_en

²⁷ <https://www.fischmagazin.de/willkommen-seriennummer-107745-Next+Tuna+GmbH.htm>

²⁸ <https://www.fischmagazin.de/willkommen-seriennummer-102902-Next+Tuna+GmbH.htm>

3.4.3 *Mission Objective*

NextTuna's activities contribute directly to multiple Mission Ocean and Waters' objectives, particularly in fostering a sustainable blue economy, protecting marine biodiversity, and promoting carbon-neutral and circular aquaculture practices. First, NextTuna is vital in protecting and restoring marine ecosystems and biodiversity. By pioneering the commercial-scale reproduction of ABT in a controlled aquaculture environment, NextTuna reduces the need for wild-caught tuna, thereby alleviating pressure on declining ABT populations, helping to restore the balance of marine food chains. Second, NextTuna contributes to the prevention and elimination of pollution in marine environments. The company's floating RAS-X system ensures zero discharge into the surrounding waters, eliminating the risk of pollution associated with traditional fish farming. Lastly, NextTuna is advancing the Mission goal to make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular. Through their floating RAS-X system, which combines the efficiency of land-based RAS with the scalability of offshore farming, NextTuna is developing a low-impact, energy-efficient aquaculture model. Their work with research partners to refine precision farming methodologies aims to reduce the carbon footprint of tuna farming.

3.4.4 *Interaction Type*

NextTuna collaborates with research institutions, private industry, and public authorities. The company works closely with [Seafarming Systems](#) and the [Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft](#) to develop precision farming methodologies for ABT and other finfish species. Additionally, the company has also formed partnerships with industry players to advance offshore capabilities and develop infrastructure that can be replicated globally. The Floating RAS-X system, developed in collaboration with Seafarming Systems, is a pivotal innovation in sustainable aquaculture, offering a flexible, scalable, and environmentally friendly solution that can be applied to other aquaculture species. The first operational floating RAS-X system will focus on Kingfish, generating early cash flow and demonstrating the viability of the technology before expanding its application to ABT. NextTuna's engagement with [the Spanish Institute of Oceanography](#) has also enabled the company to make significant strides toward commercial-scale reproduction of ABT. NextTuna's interaction with BlueInvest and the EIT Food network has been instrumental in securing funding and support for the company's growth.

3.4.5 *Implementation*

NextTuna is addressing three critical challenges in commercial ABT reproduction. Firstly, the company needs to ensure proper feeding during the crucial larvae stage, with significant progress being achieved through partnerships in Asia and Europe. Secondly, NextTuna must achieve reliable spawning in captivity. In 2023 the company had a breakthrough when their partner, the Spanish Institute of Oceanography, successfully completed the ABT reproduction cycle in a land-based RAS system. Lastly, the infrastructure has to be developed and put into place. The company's first floating RAS system is set to become operational in Spain later in 2024, representing a significant step forward for sustainable tuna farming. However, the company is first set to focus on Kingfish to generate positive cash flow and demonstrate the system's effectiveness. NextTuna aims to market its RAS-X technology to third parties while developing precision farming methodologies to optimise the system for commercial use. Lastly, by 2028, NextTuna plans to reach total capacity for ABT production, with the infrastructure designed to grow ABT to 10 kilograms before transferring them to other facilities.

3.4.6 *Outcomes*

NextTuna's efforts are not only aimed at commercial success but also at preserving marine biodiversity and promoting sustainable aquaculture. Their participation in the BlueInvest Fundraising Assistance

Programme and partnerships with key stakeholders have facilitated significant progress toward commercial-scale ABT reproduction. NextTuna won the BlueInvest Award 2023 in the category "Sustainable Food and Feed from the Ocean," reflecting the company's achievements in developing sustainable aquaculture solutions. With the successful development of the floating RAS system and continued collaboration with partners, NextTuna is positioned to revolutionise the European tuna industry while contributing to global efforts to safeguard endangered species and promote a responsible blue economy.

3.4.7 Recommendations

3.4.7.1 For Businesses

Businesses in the aquaculture sector should focus on building partnerships with universities and research institutions to advance innovation and technology. NextTuna's success in partnering with organisations such as the Spanish Institute of Oceanography and Fraunhofer highlights the importance of collaboration in tackling complex challenges like the commercial reproduction of ABT.

Moreover, businesses should be prepared for the long-term financial commitment needed to develop sustainable technologies. NextTuna emphasises that achieving results in aquaculture can take several years, particularly when working with new technologies like the Floating RAS-X system. Investment in research and development (R&D) is crucial to developing eco-friendly aquaculture practices, as seen in NextTuna's efforts and will help businesses address technical challenges more effectively. Companies should consider diversifying their early activities, as NextTuna did by focusing on Kingfish production to generate cash flow while refining their systems for ABT. Lastly, businesses should actively participate in funding programmes like BlueInvest and the EIT Food's Sustainable Aquaculture Competition, but they must also be aware of the administrative and financial challenges involved in navigating these programmes, including the need for pre-financing.

3.4.7.2 For Policymakers

Policymakers need to streamline the funding process and reduce the administrative burden for innovative startups in the blue economy. NextTuna has highlighted the complexity of securing permits and the slow processing time for approval, which can delay projects and hinder growth. By accelerating the permitting process and supporting faster regulatory approvals, policymakers can help sustainable startups scale up more quickly.

Moreover, as noted by NextTuna, navigating the EU's funding mechanisms can be burdensome, with extensive reporting requirements and slow pre-funding payouts, which can delay projects and place financial strain on smaller businesses. A more agile and flexible funding system would encourage more companies to engage with programmes like BlueInvest and EMFAF. Additionally, policymakers should focus on investor education within the blue economy. NextTuna praised BlueInvest's efforts to train investors in the blue economy, highlighting the importance of building an informed investor base to support capital-intensive projects like aquaculture. Creating financial incentives or tax breaks for businesses investing in sustainable aquaculture could further drive participation in these initiatives. By fostering investor knowledge, policymakers can bridge the funding gap and encourage more investment in sustainable marine technologies.

3.4.7.3 For Academia

Academic institutions should continue to focus on applied research that supports innovations in sustainable aquaculture, particularly in overcoming the biological and technological barriers to commercial-scale reproduction of marine species. NextTuna's collaboration with research institutions

such as Wageningen University and the Spanish Institute of Oceanography demonstrates how critical academic expertise is to advance new aquaculture technologies.

Furthermore, academia should work closely with industry to ensure that research is translated into practical solutions that can be implemented at scale. Research into precision farming methodologies, sensor technology, and sustainable infrastructure can significantly contribute to reducing the environmental impact of aquaculture while helping to achieve Mission Ocean and Waters' objectives.

3.5 DEME

3.5.1 Background

[DEME Group](#), a leading dredging and marine engineering company headquartered in Belgium, is deeply involved in projects that aim to protect and restore marine ecosystems and biodiversity, as well as support the development of a carbon-neutral and circular blue economy. Some of the key projects that DEME takes part in include [Dunefront](#) and [Coastbusters](#), dedicated to coastal protection; [Bankbusters](#), which addresses flood protection; and Reefcovery, which is dedicated to environmental restoration. DEME seeks to integrate nature-based solutions into coastal protection and environmental restoration efforts. Through these projects, DEME works closely with various stakeholders, including research institutions, to ensure that their initiatives are both scientifically sound and operationally effective.

3.5.2 Motivation for the Action

DEME's motivation for engaging in projects like Dunefront, Coastbusters, Bankbusters, and Reefcovery is driven by a combination of societal and business pressures. From a societal perspective, there is a growing concern over biodiversity loss and the associated environmental challenges, which demand innovative solutions that deliver ecosystem services. DEME recognises that society is increasingly seeking ways to address these critical issues.

On the business side, DEME is conscious that clients worldwide are increasingly facing significant challenges related to coastal defence, including erosion, sea level rise, and the increasing intensity of storms. As traditional hard infrastructure solutions become less affordable due to rising costs and maintenance needs, DEME is motivated to explore and develop more complex, multi-use solutions, such as nature-based approaches. Although requiring higher upfront capital expenditure, these nature-based approaches offer lower operational costs over the long term. The combination of the threat of biodiversity loss and the need for more sustainable infrastructure, therefore, motivates DEME's continued involvement in projects that support Mission Ocean and Waters' objectives.

3.5.3 Mission Objective

The initiatives which DEME engages with align with two key Mission Ocean and Waters objectives: protecting and restoring biodiversity and supporting a circular and sustainable blue economy. Through projects like Reefcovery, which is focused on marine ecosystem restoration, DEME directly contributes to the protection and restoration of biodiversity. Moreover, through projects like Coastbusters and Dunefront, DEME supports the development of sustainable coastal protection methods that align with the goals of a circular blue economy. These projects are primarily implemented in the North Sea and Atlantic-Arctic basins but address challenges which are increasingly relevant worldwide.

3.5.4 Interaction Type

DEME's approach to stakeholder interaction is characterised by close collaboration with research institutions from the project's inception. Key partners include the [Flanders Marine Institute \(VLIZ\)](#), the [Flemish Fisheries Institute \(ILVO\)](#), and the [University of Antwerp](#), all of whom are integral to the development and research phases of the projects. This collaboration ensures that the projects are grounded in scientific research and can address the specific environmental challenges they aim to solve. Government institutions also play a crucial role, particularly in projects like [Dunefront](#), where their involvement is necessary for obtaining permits and ensuring that the projects comply with regulatory requirements.

In 2017, DEME was also one of the companies that founded the [Blue Cluster](#) (Table 2), a non-profit organisation dedicated to improving cross-sectoral partnerships and establishing closer cooperation between knowledge centres and government agencies to encourage new investments and undertake innovative projects in the Belgian part of the North Sea and beyond.²⁹

Additionally, to this day, DEME continues to engage with local communities, especially fishermen, who provide on-the-ground insights and monitoring support. For example, fishermen have alerted DEME to issues with project infrastructure, such as sinking equipment, allowing the company to make timely adjustments.

Table 2. Blue Cluster

Blue Cluster

[The Blue Cluster \(De Blauwe Cluster\)](#) plays a pivotal role in supporting businesses like DEME, ELIA, and others in aligning their actions with Mission Ocean objectives through fostering partnerships and driving innovation in offshore economic activities. As an independent and neutral partner, Blue Cluster helps Flemish companies establish collaborations with knowledge centres, government agencies, and other businesses, ensuring that their efforts contribute to the development of a sustainable blue economy.

One of Blue Cluster’s core strategies is the organisation of “blue sessions”, where stakeholders from various sectors, such as industry and academia, come together to discuss emerging technologies and co-create solutions for challenges related to marine and maritime sectors. These sessions are specifically designed to generate new ideas and initiate collaborative projects that support the transition towards a carbon-neutral and circular blue economy. For instance, Blue Cluster has organised sessions focused on offshore floating solar and renewable energy production, which align with the goals of reducing carbon emissions and promoting sustainable energy solutions, key aspects of Mission Ocean and Waters.

In addition, every two years Blue Cluster develops a roadmap for each of its focus areas, outlining critical priorities for its operations. Blue Cluster’s roadmap on renewable energies outlines long-term objectives such as supporting the development of technologies like wind, wave, and tidal energy. These efforts contribute directly to the Mission’s aim of creating a sustainable and circular blue economy, and they provide businesses access to a wealth of knowledge and connections, facilitating the creation of projects that focus on time critical environmental sustainability and innovation.

Through these initiatives, Blue Cluster not only supports individual businesses but also creates synergies between sectors, promoting innovation that has a tangible impact on marine and freshwater ecosystems. By connecting businesses with the right expertise and funding opportunities, Blue Cluster plays an essential role in driving the blue economy forward in alignment with Mission Ocean and Waters’ objectives.

3.5.5 Implementation

Implementing these nature-based projects involves navigating several challenges, many of which are tied to the biological and environmental complexities of the marine ecosystems involved. One major challenge faced by DEME is, therefore, linked to seasonality, which determines the timing of specific

²⁹ <https://www.bluecluster.be/about/history> ; <https://www.deme-group.com/sites/default/files/2023-11/DEME-QHSES-DOC-041-E%20Participation%26Initiatives.pdf>

activities and can result in significant delays if the optimal window is missed. For instance, if permitting delays cause the project to miss a critical season, the entire project could be set back by a year.

This issue is compounded by the complex and often lengthy permitting processes required for such innovative projects. Despite these challenges, DEME remains committed to these initiatives, recognising the importance of stakeholder engagement throughout the project lifecycle. The company actively involves local communities and leverages their expertise, particularly from local fishermen, to monitor and adjust project activities as needed.

3.5.6 Outcomes

DEME's participation in the above-mentioned projects has resulted in several valuable contributions to coastal protection and marine ecosystem restoration. The expertise brought together by DEME, combined with the collaborative efforts of research institutions and local stakeholders, has led to the successful implementation of several innovative solutions. However, DEME also acknowledges the ongoing challenges, particularly the "valorisation paradox," where the societal benefits of its projects' ecosystem services are difficult to quantify in traditional economic terms, highlighting the tension between the need for immediate financial returns and the longer-term, less tangible benefits of environmental restoration.

3.5.7 Recommendations

3.5.7.1 For Businesses

Companies in the blue economy should be prepared for the complexities of stakeholder engagement and the challenges posed by permitting processes. They recommend that businesses consider nature-based solutions' long-term economic and societal benefits, even if they require higher initial investments. With regards to permitting, DEME underlines the importance of preparation, for instance, by ensuring that companies know very well the sites they are operating in and cooperating with local scientists closely, and by understanding the governance structures that influence the permitting process.

3.5.7.2 For Policymakers

Policymakers need to consider the long-term societal benefits of projects when evaluating them and to streamline permitting processes to better align with the operational needs of environmental projects.

3.6 ELIA

3.6.1 Background

[ELIA](#) is Belgium's electricity transmission system operator. It is, hence, responsible for managing the Belgian high-voltage transmission grid and ensuring that electricity production and consumption are balanced at all times.³⁰ The company is leading a groundbreaking project to construct the world's first artificial energy island in the North Sea. This energy island is designed to connect new wind farms to the mainland, enhancing interconnections with other North Sea countries. Scheduled for completion by August 2026, the project marks a significant step toward renewable energy transition. From the outset, ELIA has committed to ensuring that this project not only mitigates environmental impacts, a legal requirement under environmental impact assessment but also contributes positively to marine biodiversity, seeking to foster new marine habitats around the energy island. To achieve this, ELIA has engaged with a consortium of approximately 15 public and private institutions, universities, and NGOs. Together, they have developed a nature-inclusive design for the island that aims to foster new marine habitats, thereby enhancing biodiversity in the area.

3.6.2 Motivation for the Action

The primary motivation behind ELIA's initiative is rooted in its responsibility as a transmission system operator to act in the interest of society and to facilitate the transition towards renewable energy. Recognising the significant opportunity presented by the energy island project, ELIA was determined to ensure that the project would not only facilitate renewable energy generation but also contribute positively to marine biodiversity. This motivation stems from a broader understanding that such environmental stewardship is essential not just for legal compliance but as a "license to operate" within society. ELIA sees the integration of nature-positive measures into the project as a necessary and non-negotiable component of its business operations, reflecting a commitment to sustainable development that goes beyond financial considerations.

3.6.3 Mission Objective

[The ELIA Energy Island project](#) directly supports the Mission Ocean and Waters' objective of protecting and restoring biodiversity. The project's design incorporates nature-inclusive elements specifically tailored to enhance marine habitats in the Princess Elizabeth Zone of the North Sea, where the island is being constructed. The prioritisation of measures such as oyster and gravel beds is based on expert recommendations and aligned with public authorities' restoration goals for the region, making the project a strategic contribution to local marine biodiversity.

3.6.4 Interaction Type

ELIA's project still involves extensive interaction with a broad array of stakeholders. The company is bringing together experts from public and private institutions, universities, and NGOs to co-create the nature-inclusive design of the energy island. To manage the complexity of these collaborations, ELIA employed a neutral, independent process coordinator, whose role was crucial in facilitating discussions and ensuring that all parties could work together effectively. The process included six workshops over two years, during which experts and ELIA representatives discussed, refined, and prioritised various design measures. Additionally, ELIA engaged with the broader public and other

³⁰ <https://www.elia.be/en/company>

stakeholders through a press conference in November 2023 and made the design plans available on their website.

3.6.5 Implementation

The implementation of the energy island's nature-inclusive design presented several challenges, primarily related to coordinating the diverse group of stakeholders and integrating the technical requirements of the project with environmental goals. ELIA addressed these challenges from the start by assigning a neutral, independent process coordinator. With their assistance, ELIA and all experts on the table began the process of clearly defining the framework of ambitions and boundary conditions to facilitate decision-making at a later stage. Technical challenges, such as ensuring that nature-inclusive measures would not compromise the island's safety or increase erosion and sedimentation, were addressed through close collaboration between the experts and the island constructors. This framework guided the discussions and helped manage expectations, ensuring that the project could meet both ELIA's operational needs and the experts' biodiversity goals.

A second set of challenges was derived from the content of the solutions that the team set out to develop, and the independent process coordinator successfully addressed them. The coordinator not only facilitated discussions between all stakeholders but also consolidated the outcomes of these exchanges into actionable proposals. By conducting research independently between the sessions and offering concrete proposals for solutions at the following meetings, the coordinator optimised the experts' role as advisors rather than content producers, ensuring a smooth continuation of the process.

3.6.6 Outcomes

As a result of the collaborative process, ELIA developed a comprehensive nature-inclusive design plan that spans the entire water column, from above water to the seabed. This integrated approach is expected to create a synergistic ecosystem around the island, significantly enhancing marine biodiversity in the area. The project also provides a unique opportunity for real-life validation of expert knowledge, as the implemented measures will be monitored continuously, and the results will be shared publicly. In addition, the large surface area of the island dedicated to nature restoration is another critical outcome, as it allows for the implementation of large-scale measures that can have a meaningful impact on local biodiversity. Nowadays, part of the Princess Elizabeth project is already followed by various European universities, other offshore wind farm developers, transmission system operators like ELIA, NGOs, as well as public authorities from neighbouring European countries.

3.6.7 Recommendations

3.6.7.1 For Businesses

Companies considering similar projects should fully integrate nature-positive measures into their design plans, ensuring that they are implemented on an intrinsic and coherent scale rather than as superficial add-ons. The process of co-creation with experts and the development of an ecosystem approach, where different measures work together synergistically, are key to maximising the environmental impact of such projects.

Additionally, ELIA underlined the importance of pursuing a co-creation process involving experts and the development of an ecosystem approach, where different measures work together synergistically. This approach is key to maximising not only the environmental impact of such projects but also engaging with various stakeholders and collecting critical input.

Policymakers should support large-scale, integrated nature restoration projects that are closely aligned with local biodiversity goals. This alignment, achieved through collaboration between public authorities and project developers, ensures that available budgets are used effectively and that the projects deliver meaningful environmental benefits.

3.6.7.3 For Academia

Academic institutions should focus on applied research that supports the development and validation of similar nature-inclusive measures and certainly analyse the outputs of projects like Princess Elizabeth Island to showcase examples of exemplary ecosystem approach methodologies and their impact for future projects. Through close collaboration between academia and industry, such research findings can be effectively translated into practical solutions applicable to other basins and environments that can support Mission Ocean's Objectives.

3.6.7.4 For NGOs and Civil Society

NGOs and civil society groups should actively collaborate with businesses and public authorities. Their involvement is crucial for ensuring that nature-inclusive projects are ambitious and aligned with the specific environmental and social needs of the region.

3.7 GeoStud

3.7.1 Background

[GeoStud](#) is a Romanian SME headquartered in Bucharest. Founded in 2001, the company focuses on environmental protection and geotechnical engineering. It has established itself as a key player in environmental impact assessments, climate change studies, and circular economy principles. The company's operations include field sampling, laboratory analyses through its chemical and geotechnical labs, and the development of environmental solutions for construction and environmental protection projects. GeoStud is recognised both nationally and internationally for its contributions, particularly through projects such as [DaWetRest project](#), which focuses on the restoration of freshwater ecosystems, and the 3D initiative ([Decarbonizing Danube Delta](#)), aimed at addressing decarbonisation in the Danube Delta region.

GeoStud is also an active participant in the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters," and its involvement in the first annual forum held in Brussels in 2023 demonstrates its commitment to the Mission's objectives of reducing pollution, restoring marine and freshwater biodiversity, and promoting a sustainable blue economy. As part of the Mission, GeoStud is working towards enhancing the ecological health of water bodies, aiming to achieve significant improvements by 2030.

3.7.2 Motivation for the Action

GeoStud's motivation for its projects stems from a deep commitment to environmental sustainability and social responsibility. The company's focus is not only on immediate financial returns but also on creating long-term environmental and social value. As expressed by their leadership during recent forums, GeoStud aims to be a reference point in geotechnical and environmental studies both in Romania and internationally. This vision is driven by the need to integrate climate change mitigation, circular economy principles, and environmental conservation into their operations. Their efforts in the DaWetRest project and the 3D initiative reflect a broader goal to influence policy frameworks in Romania while fostering sustainability practices that balance the needs of local communities with the preservation of natural ecosystems.

3.7.3 Mission Objective

GeoStud's activities align with several objectives of the Mission Ocean and Waters, particularly in biodiversity protection and pollution reduction. The mission core of the DaWetRest project is to restore biodiversity in the Danube-Black Sea basin, addressing the degradation of freshwater ecosystems. Their geotechnical and chemical labs play a pivotal role in ensuring that their environmental assessments meet the highest standards, which contributes to sustainable practices in both environmental restoration and construction projects. Furthermore, GeoStud actively contributes to the circular economy by incorporating these principles into national reports and studies, shaping environmental agreements and construction permits in Romania.

3.7.4 Interaction Type

GeoStud's interaction with stakeholders is extensive and includes collaborations with public authorities, NGOs, academia, and local communities. They work closely with the Romanian Ministry of Environment, Waters, and Forests, ensuring that their studies and recommendations are integrated into national legislation. Their participation in international forums, such as the "Restore our Ocean

and Waters" Mission forum, highlights their proactive role in shaping EU-wide initiatives related to freshwater and marine ecosystems.³¹

GeoStud also engages with local communities and NGOs through its NGO, [Natura 5](#), which serves as a bridge between scientific research and public understanding. This NGO was established by some company employees with the intention of translating complex scientific concepts into accessible information for local communities. The goal of the NGO is to ensure that such communities are well-informed and hence able to actively engage in environmental conservation efforts in the region.

Additionally, GeoStud participates in international collaborations, such as their work with Egyptian partners in the 3D initiative, to exchange best practices and expand their environmental impact beyond Romania.

3.7.5 Implementation

GeoStud implements its projects through a data-driven approach that includes extensive field sampling, laboratory analysis, and stakeholder engagement. Their work in projects like DaWetRest and the 3D initiative highlights the importance of multidisciplinary collaboration to achieve the decarbonisation of the Danube Delta and the restoration of biodiversity. GeoStud's participation in the first annual forum of the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters" emphasised their commitment to achieving tangible environmental outcomes by 2030, particularly in the areas of biodiversity restoration and pollution reduction. The company's NGO, Natura 5, plays a vital role in ensuring that local communities are engaged and well informed about the environmental impact of these projects.

3.7.6 Outcomes

GeoStud's efforts have significantly improved biodiversity restoration and environmental monitoring. Through the DaWetRest project, they have made concrete contributions to restoring freshwater ecosystems, which are critical to maintaining the ecological balance of the Danube-Black Sea basin. Their work in the 3D initiative has positioned GeoStud as a leader in the decarbonisation of the Danube Delta, contributing to the EU's Fit for 55 plan. The company's recognition at international forums further underscores its expanding role in addressing environmental challenges at both national and global levels. Moreover, creating Natura 5 has further enhanced GeoStud's ability to engage with local communities, raising awareness about environmental issues and promoting sustainable practices at the grassroots level. Additionally, GeoStud's international collaborations, such as their partnership with Egyptian entities, have expanded the reach of their environmental initiatives and allowed them to share their best practices on a global scale.

3.7.7 Recommendations

3.7.7.1 For Businesses

GeoStud recommends that businesses in the environmental sector focus on long-term collaboration and international partnerships. Their experience in working with academia, public authorities, and international stakeholders has proven that the most impactful projects arise from strong partnerships. Additionally, they advise businesses to commit to integrating circular economy principles and environmental protection into their core operations to create sustainable growth.

³¹ <https://www.digi24.ro/stiri/sci-tech/natura-si-mediu/p-geostud-alaturi-de-initiativa-3d-prezenti-la-primul-forum-anual-al-misiunii-ue-restore-our-ocean-and-waters-2258397>

GeoStud highlights the need for better data availability and support from public authorities in performing baseline environmental assessments. They recommend that policymakers invest in data collection and make high-quality environmental data more accessible to ensure that businesses can make informed decisions. In line with their experience in Romania, GeoStud advocates for the inclusion of SMEs in environmental monitoring to ensure transparency and independence in reporting.

3.7.7.3 For NGOs and Civil Society

GeoStud advises NGOs to focus on effective communication and translation of scientific data for local communities. They believe that NGOs play a crucial role in bridging the gap between businesses, scientific research, and the public, and can help ensure that environmental protection efforts are understood and supported at the grassroots level. GeoStud's experience with their own NGO, Natura 5, demonstrates the value of this approach in engaging local communities and fostering a deeper understanding of environmental issues.

3.7.7.4 For Academia

GeoStud recommends that academic institutions continue to collaborate with industry to produce applied research that supports environmental protection initiatives. Their close collaboration with research institutes and universities has been instrumental in developing innovative environmental solutions. They also suggest that universities play a more active role in nurturing the next generation of environmental experts by offering hands-on training and collaborative research opportunities.

3.8 Kongsberg

3.8.1 Background

[Kongsberg](#) is a Norwegian technology company providing advanced systems for positioning, surveying, navigation, and automation for both merchant vessels and offshore installations. As a global leader in maritime technology, Kongsberg delivers innovative solutions aimed at reducing environmental impact, improving efficiency, and enabling more sustainable maritime operations. Their systems play a key role in supporting Mission Ocean and Waters' objectives, particularly in the shipping sector, but also concerning areas related to reducing emissions, improving marine biodiversity, and fostering a sustainable blue economy.

[Kongsberg Maritime](#) division's business spans a range of cutting-edge technologies designed to enhance sustainability across the maritime sector.³² They specialise in ship design featuring alternative fuel power plants, which help vessels transition to cleaner energy sources. Their energy-efficient vessel systems aim to reduce fuel consumption and emissions, making maritime operations greener and more cost-effective.

Additionally, the [Kongsberg Discovery](#) division provides sensor solutions for measuring ocean health, enabling real-time monitoring of water quality, pollution levels, and ecosystem conditions, which are crucial for marine conservation efforts. The company is also a leader in intelligent fishing solutions that target specific species, minimising bycatch and reducing the collateral environmental damage caused by traditional fishing methods. To further improve operational efficiency, Kongsberg Discovery also offers voyage optimisation solutions, which allow vessels to minimise fuel consumption and emissions by optimising their routes.

3.8.2 Motivation for the Action

Kongsberg is driven by a commitment to enable more sustainable operations in the maritime sector, balancing environmental stewardship with business opportunities. As a key player in the transition to greener maritime technologies, Kongsberg is motivated by the growing demand for environmentally responsible solutions that reduce the harmful impacts of maritime operations, such as fuel consumption and emissions. Their business model focuses on offering advanced technologies that align with global sustainability goals while providing value to their customers through increased operational efficiency.

However, one of the main challenges Kongsberg faces is convincing customers to invest in technologies that go beyond regulatory requirements. Kongsberg emphasises that most customers expect a payback period of around five years on their investments. If the payback period extends beyond this, for instance, to ten years, customers are less inclined to invest. This creates a challenge in promoting additional investment in environmentally friendly technologies, as longer payback periods may be seen as reducing competitiveness. To overcome this, Kongsberg is committed to demonstrating its solutions' long-term cost savings and efficiency improvements, seeking to encourage more businesses to make these investments. The company sees its role as not only a technology provider but also an advisor, helping customers understand the potential benefits of adopting sustainable practices beyond mere compliance.

³² <https://www.kongsberg.com/maritime/solutions/>

3.8.3 *Mission Objective*

Kongsberg's work contributes to several Mission Ocean and Waters goals, particularly in supporting the development of a sustainable blue economy and reducing the environmental impacts of maritime operations. Their technologies directly address the need for sustainable energy use in shipping while offering innovative solutions that help minimise the harm to marine ecosystems. The company's energy-efficient vessel systems and alternative fuel-powered ship designs aim to reduce fuel consumption and emissions, helping to decrease the pollution that threatens ocean health and biodiversity. Moreover, Kongsberg's intelligent fishing solutions also have the potential to contribute to the objective of protecting marine ecosystems and biodiversity, through their use of sensor technology and artificial intelligence to target specific fish species. By reducing bycatch and minimising collateral damage to non-target species, this technology helps to protect marine biodiversity, preventing the overexploitation of vulnerable species and reducing the destruction of marine habitats. These targeted fishing methods not only enhance the efficiency of fishing operations but also support efforts in line with the goals of Mission Ocean and Waters.

3.8.4 *Interaction Type*

Kongsberg collaborates extensively with research institutes, universities, and class societies to develop their technological solutions. Notably, they work closely with [University of South-Eastern Norway](#), the [Havforskningsintitutt](#) (Norwegian Institute of Marine Research) and the [Norwegian University of Science and Technology](#) (NTNU). With the University of South-Eastern Norway, the company has collaborated alongside several other companies to establish an industrial master's program that allows students to pursue a part-time master's degree while engaging in relevant work within the company.³³ With [Havforskningsintitutt](#), the company is collaborating on creating their advanced sensor technology, used to gather data on pollution levels, ocean health, and other environmental indicators.³⁴ These partnerships enable Kongsberg Maritime to stay at the cutting edge of technological development, ensuring their products align with scientific research and environmental objectives.

3.8.5 *Implementation*

Kongsberg initiatives focus on developing high-efficiency maritime technologies and ensuring their replicability across regions and maritime sectors. For example, their smart fishing solutions use sensor technologies and artificial intelligence to target specific species, thereby reducing bycatch and the environmental damage caused by traditional fishing methods. Although the adoption of these technologies can be costly, these products increase operational efficiency, allowing customers to reduce fuel consumption and man-hours, which provides a clear business case for investment. However, challenges persist in convincing some customers, especially smaller operators or those in regions like the Mediterranean, where fishing is less industrialised, to invest in these technologies.

3.8.6 *Outcomes*

Through their collaboration with universities, class societies, and industry stakeholders, Kongsberg has developed an extensive range of innovative products that are helping to transform the maritime industry. Their sensor technologies are widely used and sold not only to private sector actors but also to academic institutions to monitor ocean health, offering critical data and insights needed for

³³ <https://www.kongsberg.com/careers/industry-master-programmes/>

³⁴ <https://www.hi.no/hi/nyheter/2019/juli/kongsberg-seminar-om-berekraftige-hav>

research and restoration projects. Moreover, their energy-efficient systems and smart fishing solutions have been successfully implemented on large vessels not only in Europe but around the world, supporting various businesses in improving their operational efficiency while reducing their environmental impact at sea. Kongsberg is also committed to developing technologies with a wide geographical application focus and replicability to ensure that these solutions can be adopted across different regions, extending the company's impact beyond Northern Europe to markets in India, Japan, Australia, and beyond.

In addition to its technological advancements, Kongsberg also actively supports educational initiatives aimed at fostering education, research, and innovation in ocean-related fields. Through its collaboration with the University of South-Eastern Norway and the establishment of a master's degree, Kongsberg is playing an active role also in shaping the future of the sector, supporting the development of critical blue tech skills necessary further to support the transition to a blue circular economy. Moreover, the company has continuously engaged in student engagement events such as YOUR EXTREME, an annual case competition in collaboration with NTNU and the University of South-Eastern Norway since 2013.³⁵ This 48-hour case competition challenges students to develop creative tech and sustainable solutions to address future challenges. In 2018, the competition focused on developing sustainable aquaculture systems, with the winning team proposing a circular economy-based solution that minimises resource waste.³⁶ Through this initiative, Kongsberg demonstrates a long-term commitment to supporting technological innovation in sustainable ocean management.

3.8.7 Recommendations

3.8.7.1 For Businesses

Businesses in the maritime sector should prioritise long-term investments in sustainable technologies as part of their core operations rather than viewing them as optional or secondary to compliance. Kongsberg's technologies demonstrate that there are significant opportunities for operational efficiencies, cost savings, and competitive advantages for those willing to invest in energy-efficient and eco-friendly systems. Businesses should also engage in partnerships with research institutions and universities to stay at the cutting edge of innovation, ensuring that they are not only meeting today's regulatory requirements but also preparing for future shifts toward sustainability.

However, Kongsberg emphasises that most customers expect a payback period of around five years on their investments. If the payback period extends beyond this, closer to ten years, customers are less inclined to invest. This highlights the importance of businesses working with external partners or leveraging funding schemes to make longer-term investments more attractive and feasible.

Furthermore, businesses can benefit from engaging with universities on educational initiatives that build staff competence in sustainable practices and new technologies, as well as engaging with future professionals to promote interest in young students in pursuing a career in the marine tech sector and fostering long-term industry growth, a vital part of supporting a sustainable blue economy.

3.8.7.2 For Policymakers

To accelerate the adoption of sustainable maritime technologies, policymakers should create enabling frameworks that encourage investment in green technologies. Kongsberg's experience highlights that many maritime operators hesitate to invest in technologies that go beyond regulatory requirements

³⁵ <https://www.kongsberg.com/yourextreme/>

³⁶ <https://www.kongsberg.com/careers/students/your-extreme/>

due to the longer payback periods associated with these investments. As mentioned, most customers expect a payback period of around five years, but if the investment payback stretches to ten years or more, they are less inclined to commit. To overcome this, policymakers should consider implementing targeted subsidies, tax incentives, or funding schemes that help reduce the financial burden and shorten the payback period for businesses willing to adopt these sustainable technologies.

Additionally, regulatory frameworks should focus on setting achievable, phased goals for emissions reductions, energy efficiency, and marine biodiversity protection. Policymakers should co-create these regulations with industry stakeholders to ensure they are ambitious and realistic, fostering an environment where businesses feel confident making long-term investments that contribute to sustainability goals.

3.8.7.3 For Academia

There is a growing need for applied research that directly supports the technological advancements required to meet sustainability goals in the maritime sector. Universities and research institutions should focus on developing solutions that are not only innovative but also scalable and commercially viable. Collaborations between academia and industry, such as Kongsberg's partnerships with the University of South-Eastern Norway and the Norwegian Institute of Marine Research, should be encouraged and expanded to ensure that research outcomes have real-world applicability.

Academic institutions should also expand interdisciplinary educational programmes, combining engineering, sustainability, and marine science, to train the next generation of blue economy professionals. Programmes such as the industrial master's program in partnership with Kongsberg are excellent examples of how academia can actively contribute to industry-relevant skills development.

3.9 Easy Harvest

3.9.1 Background

[Easy Harvest](#) is an innovative startup based in the Algarve region of Portugal, focusing on the sustainable collection and utilisation of seaweed. The company was founded by Francisco Machado, a marine biologist with a passion for aquaculture and seaweed, who was later joined by Emilia Kotiranta, who has a management background. Francisco, who has a background in marine aquaculture, was initially inspired by the potential of seaweed farming but later shifted his focus after recognising the challenges and bottlenecks in the viability of seaweed aquaculture. Instead, with Emilia, they observed that the Algarve coastline was increasingly affected by seaweed blooms, which were discarded as waste despite having significant potential as a resource.

From this phenomenon, they derived the idea to address the environmental and economic impacts of seaweed blooms, which can disrupt local ecosystems, fisheries, and tourism. The company has developed an innovative approach to harvesting seaweed, utilising a vacuum-like system to collect seaweed floating in the water before it strands on beaches. This method mitigates the environmental impact and provides a sustainable source of biomass that can be used in various industries, including fertilisers, animal feed, and bio-based materials. However, Easy Harvest also monitors seaweed blooms and provides constant data, reports, and estimates to municipalities and other stakeholders.

The startup collaborates with several key stakeholders, including the [University of Algarve's Centre of Marine Sciences](#) (CCMAR), which supports research and development efforts. Easy Harvest also works closely with local municipalities and governmental bodies, such as the [Directorate-General for Natural Resources, Safety, and Maritime Services \(DGRM\)](#), to obtain necessary permits and ensure compliance with environmental regulations. Their work has led to the issuance of an experimental fisheries authorisation, allowing them to explore new techniques for sustainable seaweed collection.

Through their efforts, Easy Harvest addresses an environmental challenge and aims to create economic opportunities in the region. The company is dedicated to promoting the use of seaweed as a valuable resource, rather than waste, and is working towards expanding its operations and establishing itself as a seaweed supplier in Europe. Their innovative approach and focus on sustainability position Easy Harvest as a key player in the emerging blue economy, contributing to the protection and restoration of marine ecosystems.

3.9.2 Motivation for the Action

Easy Harvest's motivation is rooted in both personal and environmental concerns. Co-founder Francisco expressed a strong desire to create job opportunities within Portugal, enabling people like himself to stay in their home country rather than seek work abroad. This personal motivation aligns with a broader mission to address the environmental issues caused by seaweed blooms, which have increasingly affected the Algarve region. The founders recognised that the seaweed, often treated as waste and discarded by municipalities, could be a valuable resource if harvested and processed effectively. By developing a method to collect and utilise the seaweed, Easy Harvest aims to mitigate the negative impacts on tourism, local fisheries, and coastal ecosystems while simultaneously creating a new economic opportunity. The company is committed to reducing waste and contributing to sustainable practices, viewing its actions as essential for preserving the environment and local livelihoods.

3.9.3 Mission Objective

Easy Harvest’s activities align closely with the Mission Ocean and Waters’ objectives of protecting and restoring biodiversity and supporting a circular and sustainable blue economy. The company addresses the issue of invasive seaweed species that threaten local biodiversity by collecting them before they reach the beaches and cause ecological damage. This approach helps to maintain the health of coastal ecosystems and reduces the adverse effects on marine life. Additionally, their technologies support the protection and restoration of marine ecosystems by promoting a sustainable farming method that ensures minimal disturbance to local biodiversity. By turning the harvested seaweed into valuable products, Easy Harvest also promotes a circular economy model, ensuring that natural resources are utilised efficiently and sustainably. Their operations are focused on the Atlantic basin, particularly along the Portuguese coast, where seaweed blooms are a significant environmental concern.

3.9.4 Interaction Type

Easy Harvest engages with a wide range of stakeholders, including scientific institutions, government bodies, local municipalities, and industry partners. The company collaborates closely with CCMAR at the University of Algarve, leveraging its scientific expertise to conduct research on the environmental impact of seaweed harvesting and to optimise their harvesting methods. The partnership with CCMAR provides Easy Harvest with valuable insights into seaweed ecology and supports their efforts to develop sustainable harvesting techniques and refine their monitoring techniques. Easy Harvest also works with DGRM to secure the authorisation of experimental fisheries, allowing them to harvest seaweed legally in a novel manner. This regulatory interaction is crucial for ensuring that their operations are compliant with national laws and environmental standards. Additionally, Easy Harvest engages regularly with local municipalities and local governmental authorities to understand their needs and concerns, providing reports and data on the environmental and social impacts of seaweed blooms. This side of the public sector recognised the project's potential early on and supported the company in seeking authorisation and beginning their operations in the region. Lastly, Easy Harvest is a member of BlueBio Alliance (Table 3), which offers Easy Harvest a critical connection to relevant regional and international stakeholders, as well as the opportunity to participate in strategic events and activities that can support its project and offer it visibility.

Table 3. BlueBio Alliance

BlueBio Alliance

The BlueBio Alliance (BBA), founded in Portugal in 2015, plays a crucial role in supporting the marine bioresources and blue biotechnology sectors, particularly by helping Portuguese companies align with Mission Ocean objectives. As a national association with over 200 members from across the value chain, including raw material producers, research centres, startups, SMEs, large companies, and public sector entities, BBA fosters innovation and collaboration to drive sustainable blue growth.

BBA’s mission is to promote and develop the blue bioresources sector, with the goal of creating jobs and increasing value creation for Portugal. It acts as a facilitator for the blue bioeconomy by organizing the marine bioresources value chain and helping SMEs grow and internationalise. BBA provides its members with access to infrastructure, services, and facilities that support marine bio-based innovations, while also offering platforms for collaboration and knowledge exchange. The association regularly organizes webinars on topics such as collaborative debt financing,

European funding opportunities, science communication, and sustainable business strategies, offering critical insights for companies looking to innovate and align with sustainability goals.

BBA also manages the [Blue Demo Network](#), a platform designed to promote blue bioeconomy services and infrastructures to startups. The network offers a comprehensive range of services, including access to state-of-the-art facilities for the production of marine bioresources, process technology and testing, marketing and sales support, and business development services such as mentoring and intellectual property management. Moreover, BBA is a partner in the [Blue Bio Value](#) accelerator program, which supports startups offering sustainable ocean-based solutions. The program helps scale marine bio-based projects, accelerating startups that create sustainable products and services in the blue biotechnology sector. The programme is sponsored by the [Oceano Azul Foundation](#), which similarly to BBA is committed to driving the blue bioeconomy forward in Portugal, ensuring that businesses contribute to sustainable economic growth without damaging the ocean environment.

Additionally, BBA acts as a national voice for the sector, engaging with national government entities on policy briefs, and working with European institutions to secure funding through programmes like Horizon 2020.

3.9.5 Implementation

Implementing Easy Harvest's seaweed harvesting operations involves using a specialised system similar to aquaculture pumps, which allows them to collect seaweed floating in the water before it reaches the shore. This method minimises environmental disruption and avoids the collection of sand, which often contaminates seaweed when collected directly from beaches. Easy Harvest also continuously monitors algae blooms, providing data and impact assessments to local authorities. This monitoring process is essential for understanding their operations' long-term ecological impact and making necessary adjustments. The company is currently focused on increasing the scale of its operations, aiming to harvest more significant quantities of seaweed by investing in more advanced equipment and refining its collection techniques.

3.9.6 Outcomes

Easy Harvest has successfully implemented its seaweed harvesting model, reaching an initial milestone of collecting three tonnes of seaweed in 2024. While this is not a large harvest, this achievement demonstrates the feasibility of their approach and the potential for scaling up. Moreover, by harvesting seaweed before it strands on beaches, Easy Harvest helps to maintain cleaner coastal areas, which benefits both tourism and local fisheries. The collected seaweed produces various products, turning what was previously considered waste into a valuable resource. The company's operations have provided valuable insights into the ecological impacts of seaweed blooms, contributing to a better understanding of how to manage and mitigate these environmental challenges. Easy Harvest's ongoing collaboration with scientific institutions and local authorities ensures that their activities are aligned with broader environmental and economic goals.

3.9.7 Recommendations

3.9.7.1 For Businesses

Companies should stay adaptable and open to changing their business models in response to market demands and environmental challenges. Building strong relationships with local stakeholders, including municipalities and research institutions, is crucial for gaining support and ensuring the sustainability of operations. Companies should focus on understanding the specific environmental and cultural contexts in which they operate to address local issues effectively.

3.9.7.2 For Policymakers

Policymakers should provide clear and supportive frameworks for experimental projects that address environmental issues. Streamlining communication and approval processes for permits and licenses can help facilitate innovative business solutions. Policymakers should also recognise startups' potential to contribute to local economies and environmental conservation and provide the necessary support to help these businesses succeed.

3.9.7.3 For NGOs and Civil Society

NGOs and civil society organisations should actively engage with startups and provide platforms for collaboration and knowledge sharing. Building networks and fostering communication between different stakeholders can enhance the effectiveness of environmental initiatives. NGOs can play a key role in raising awareness and educating the public about the value of sustainable practices and the benefits of utilising natural resources responsibly.

3.9.7.4 For Academia

Researchers can provide essential insights into the environmental impact of business activities and help develop innovative solutions that balance economic viability with ecological sustainability. Academic institutions should continue to support applied research that directly contributes to solving real-world environmental challenges.

3.10 BAMS Innovation Space

3.10.1 Background

[BaMS \(Bioeconomy at Marine Sites\)](#) Association is a network of organisations based in Germany committed to supporting the development of a circular and carbon-neutral blue bioeconomy. Within the association, the BaMS innovation space is an initiative, connected to the association, and coordinated by Kiel University, which receives funding from the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF), with up to €20 million allocated over a five-year period from 2019 to 2024. Through the Innovation Space, BaMS aims to foster innovation by supporting projects focused on developing sustainable marine and freshwater bioeconomy solutions, targeting sectors such as aquaculture, algae production, water management, and renewable energies.

BaMS' primary goal is to foster solutions that contribute to a circular blue bioeconomy, focusing on producing biomass, developing sector-connecting solutions, and processing marine biomass to create higher-value products. To ensure the long-term sustainability of the network, BaMS has also established a legal entity, BaMS e.V., which will continue to support the innovation space initiative even after the federal funding ends in 2025.

3.10.2 Motivation for the Action

BaMS' motivation lies in creating a sustainable blue bioeconomy, recognising that this approach is essential for replacing fossil fuel-based carbon with bio-based renewable carbon. The association aims to accelerate the transition toward climate-friendly and circular economic practices, leveraging the unique opportunities provided by marine and freshwater ecosystems. The BaMS innovation space allows businesses to engage in high-risk research they wouldn't normally undertake independently, offering access to specific knowledge and expertise from research institutions that would otherwise be too expensive. The team behind BaMS is mainly motivated by their belief in the future of the blue bioeconomy as a key pillar of global sustainability. By bringing together diverse stakeholders, including businesses, researchers, and policymakers, BaMS fosters a collaborative environment that allows for the exchange of ideas and the development of new business models that can support the establishment of a sustainable blue bioeconomy in Germany.

3.10.3 Mission Objective

Through both the association and the Innovation Space, BaMS directly supports the Mission Ocean and Waters objectives by promoting the development of a carbon-neutral and circular blue bioeconomy. The projects within BaMS focus on creating sustainable solutions that reduce the environmental footprint of marine-based industries while fostering economic resilience. One of the critical aspects of BaMS' work is its emphasis on cross-sector collaboration, particularly in integrating solutions that span multiple industries, such as the [Urban Aqua project](#), which combines sectors like aquaculture, microalgae production, and agriculture to create a closed-loop system that maximises resource efficiency. BaMS' mission also aligns with the intention to protect and restore biodiversity, as many supported projects focus on reducing environmental degradation and enhancing ecosystem resilience. By funding projects that process marine biomass and develop innovative bio-based products, BaMS also helps reduce the reliance on non-renewable resources and promotes the sustainable use of marine ecosystems.

3.10.4 Interaction Type

The BaMS Innovation Space facilitates a broad range of interactions between businesses, research institutions, universities, local communities, and federal agencies, creating a well-connected network that spans multiple sectors within the blue bioeconomy. Collaboration is central to BaMS' success, bringing together stakeholders from different industries to solve complex challenges related to marine and freshwater ecosystems, bioresource management, and sustainability.³⁷

The 42 members of the innovation space include leading universities, research institutions, and SMEs from across Germany, all involved in cross-sector collaboration that focuses on developing innovative bioeconomic models. For example, funded projects such as the [BioFiA](#) and [OptiRAS](#) projects focused on optimising fish farming in aquaculture, emphasise the importance of fostering collaboration across different industries and sectors to tackle sustainability challenges. In light of this, the association and the innovation space engage with maritime, shipping, agriculture, and aquaculture sectors, also working closely with organisations such as the [SUBMARINER Network for Blue Growth](#) (Table 4) and the [European Aquaculture Technology and Innovation Platform](#).³⁸ To support collaboration, BaMS also operates through an online platform, enabling its members to exchange knowledge, share project updates, and collaborate more effectively. The BaMS project office, located in the Kiel Science Center, provides coordination and strategic guidance for members, ensuring that projects are aligned with the roadmap for achieving a circular blue bioeconomy.

BaMS also actively engages with local communities and policymakers, ensuring that its projects not only contribute to academic and business innovation but also generate social and environmental benefits for the broader public. Demonstration sites, supported by accompanying research projects, serve as public models that show how circular economy principles can be applied to real-world settings. BaMS also participates in national and European-level policy discussions on the future of the blue bioeconomy. By working with federal agencies and international bodies, BaMS ensures that the outcomes of its projects contribute to the broader goals of sustainability, climate protection, and economic development, including the objectives set by Mission Ocean.

Table 4. SUBMARINER Network for Blue Growth

SUBMARINER Network for Blue Growth

[The SUBMARINER Network for Blue Growth](#) is a transnational platform in the Baltic Sea Region, committed to promoting innovative and sustainable uses of marine resources. Founded in 2013, the Network brings together research institutions, private companies, authorities, and civil society to foster a healthy ocean and a productive, circular blue economy. As a flagship initiative under the [EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region \(EUSBSR\)](#), the SUBMARINER Network plays a vital role in aligning regional efforts with global frameworks, as reflected in its work as coordinator of the [Horizon CSA Blue Mission BANOS](#), supporting actions in both the Baltic and North Sea Lighthouse areas as part of the EU's Mission Ocean and Waters. While rooted in the Baltic Sea Region, the SUBMARINER Network extends its partnerships beyond this geographical base, engaging with actors across Europe and globally. This cross-border collaboration ensures that the Network serves as a bridge between the Baltic Sea and other sea basins, facilitating the exchange of knowledge and best practices.

³⁷ <https://blaue-biooekonomie.de/en/about/members-institutions>

³⁸ <https://blaue-biooekonomie.de/en/projects>

SUBMARINER's vision revolves around five key objectives: mitigating climate change, increasing biodiversity, protecting the environment, reducing pollution, and fostering sustainable development. The Network promotes the circular economy, encourages renewable energy production, and supports sustainable food systems, all while ensuring that economic activities in coastal regions generate livelihoods and job opportunities for communities. The Network's projects also promote the restoration of ecosystems and the creation of marine protection areas through innovative concepts like multi-use, marine spatial planning and 'building with nature.' [SUBMARINER's Roadmap Beyond 2021](#) lays out a strategic vision for scaling up blue economy initiatives, advancing marine innovations, and integrating circular business models. It highlights the importance of partnerships, technology transfer, and practical solutions to foster the sustainable use of marine resources.

3.10.5 Implementation

The BaMS Innovation Space follows a well-structured approach to implementing its projects, focusing on cross-sector collaboration, data-driven research, and long-term sustainability. Each project is selected based on its alignment with the [BaMS Roadmap](#), which outlines key steps toward achieving a circular blue bioeconomy. Projects within BaMS are not only evaluated for their scientific and technical merit but also for their potential to contribute to the broader societal and environmental goals of the blue bioeconomy.

The implementation strategy is centred on three key areas of action:

1. **Transfer Acceleration:** This involves the rapid implementation of R&D projects that contribute to the development of BaMS biorefineries. These projects focus on utilising aquatic resources, such as fish, algae, and mussels, to create sustainable and ecologically sensitive production systems. [BioFiA](#) and [OptiRAS](#), for instance, aim to optimise aquaculture conditions, making them more sustainable and resource-efficient.
2. **Increase in Acceptance Through Education:** One of BaMS' critical objectives is to create model locations that serve as demonstration sites for circular economy principles in action. These sites are designed to educate the public, local stakeholders, and policymakers on how innovative bioeconomic systems can function. This helps increase public acceptance of sustainable practices and facilitates the transfer of knowledge into industry and society.
3. **Proximity to Application:** BaMS projects are designed to ensure that research outcomes are not just theoretical but can be applied directly to real-world scenarios. This is seen in projects such as [BALI](#) and [LaMuOpt](#), which focus on the sustainable use of regionally produced algae and mussels to develop high-value products for industries like cosmetics and pharmaceuticals and create sustainable fish feed.

BaMS projects are implemented through R&D consortia, groups formed at the start of each initiative consisting of universities, research institutions, companies, and other actors in the blue bioeconomy. Each consortium is responsible for driving forward its specific area of research, ensuring that progress is made toward the broader goals of sustainability and circularity in marine and freshwater systems. Furthermore, BaMS ensures that its projects are supported by accompanying research, which provides the scientific underpinning for long-term success. These research efforts focus on integrating digital tools, science communication, and sector coupling (the interaction between energy, water, and material flows) to enhance the scalability and replicability of BaMS innovations. BaMS also prioritises stakeholder engagement, working closely with local communities and industry partners to ensure that

the outcomes of the projects align with both regional and national sustainability goals. This approach guarantees that BaMS innovations are not only cutting-edge but also practical and widely accepted.

3.10.6 Outcomes

BaMS has successfully created a vibrant network of businesses and research institutions working together to foster innovation in the blue bioeconomy. The initiative has funded 29 projects to date, each contributing to the development of sustainable solutions for marine and freshwater ecosystems. One of the most significant outcomes of BaMS' work is its ability to bring together diverse stakeholders and encourage cross-sector collaboration.

One notable example of a project supported by BaMS' innovation space is the [Urban Aqua](#) project, which leverages waste heat from industrial sites to support aquaculture, microalgae production, and agriculture. The aim of the project is to develop an aquaponic pilot plant for the urban circular economy at the Acheron GmbH site on Bremen Übersee Island. To this end, the Bremen companies [Acheron GmbH](#), [Farmcycle GmbH](#) and [Polyplan-Kreikenbaum Gruppe GmbH](#) are cooperating with the research facilities of the [Alfred Wegener Institute](#) and with the [University of Bremen](#) and the [Bremerhaven University of Applied Sciences](#). The overall objective of the consortium is to demonstrate that sustainable production of fish and vegetable products is feasible through the best possible circulation in the middle of the city. This is to be achieved through the bioconversion of residues containing nitrogen and phosphorus-containing and the utilisation of by-products produced on-site. The project work focuses on developing an aquaponics system for breeding freshwater fish and leafy vegetables with integrated microalgae cultivation, water lenses, and insect breeding, the associated measurement and control technology, and sustainable energy and marketing concepts. By the end of 2025, the goal is to produce fresh and healthy food sustainably within the pilot.³⁹

By 2025, BaMS aims to have established itself as a self-sustaining network, continuing its work even after federal funding ends. The creation of BaMS e.V. ensures that the network will have the financial and organisational structure needed to continue supporting innovation in the blue bioeconomy.

3.10.7 Recommendations

3.10.7.1 For Businesses

Businesses in the blue bioeconomy sector should consider joining associations like BaMS to access co-funded, high-risk research opportunities and collaborate with research institutions. The innovation space enables businesses to experiment with new technologies and develop sustainable solutions without bearing the full financial burden. Additionally, companies can benefit from cross-sector collaborations that allow them to diversify their business models and tap into new markets, as seen with the Urban Aqua project.

3.10.7.2 For Policymakers

Policymakers should provide long-term funding mechanisms to support initiatives like BaMS' innovation space, which have proven effective in fostering innovation in the blue bioeconomy. Additionally, simplifying the application and reporting processes for businesses and research institutions can encourage greater participation in these initiatives. Furthermore, policies that promote cross-sector collaboration and public-private partnerships can help scale the impact of similar blue bioeconomy projects.

³⁹ <https://www.awi.de/forschung/besondere-gruppen/aquakultur/aquakulturforschung/projekte/urbanaqua.html>

Academic institutions should continue to engage with and focus on applied research that supports the development of sustainable blue bioeconomy solutions. Collaborating with businesses and other stakeholders through associations like BaMS and opportunities like its innovation space can ensure that research findings are translated into practical applications. Additionally, academia can play a critical role in educating the next generation of professionals in the blue economy, ensuring that they have the skills and knowledge needed to contribute to this growing field.

3.10.7.4 For NGOs and Civil Society

NGOs and civil society organisations can contribute to the success of blue bioeconomy projects by engaging local communities in sustainable initiatives. By collaborating with businesses, academia, and policymakers, NGOs can help ensure that sustainability goals are met and that the benefits of these projects are shared across society. Raising awareness about the potential of the blue bioeconomy and advocating for sustainable practices will be critical in driving long-term change.

3.11 Occitane Region

3.11.1 Background

Occitanie, located in Southern France, is one of the country's largest regions, stretching from the Mediterranean Sea to the Pyrenees and covering a significant portion of France's coastline. With its strategic maritime location and diverse natural landscapes, Occitanie plays a crucial role in France's blue economy, making it a hub for marine and maritime activities. The region's coastal economy is supported by a wide range of industries, including fisheries, shipping, tourism, and renewable energy, all of which are integral to the local economy.⁴⁰

Recognising the importance of balancing economic growth with environmental sustainability, the region has taken significant steps to promote the blue economy through multi-sector collaboration. One of the region's hallmark initiatives is the *Contrat de Filière* (sector contract), specifically focused on the nautical sector. This initiative was co-developed through consultations with over 60 companies, engaged over the course of 3 months to identify key challenges and establish a roadmap for sustainable growth. The *Contrat de Filière* is a testament to the region's commitment to fostering innovation and creating resilient, sustainable industries.

The *Avenir Littoral* programme is another notable initiative to address the challenges facing the region's coastline. Launched to support innovation in response to coastal erosion, marine submersion, and pollution, this programme promotes the development of technological solutions and innovative practices to protect coastal areas. Through *Avenir Littoral*, the region aims to safeguard its natural resources while fostering sustainable economic growth in maritime sectors.

In addition to its economic initiatives, the Occitanie region has implemented environmental projects such as *Alliance Posidonie*, which protects marine ecosystems, and the *Label Bateau Bleu* project, in which the region funds stickers and information panels for boat hire companies. Moreover, the region also seeks to support startups and SMEs working on blue economy subjects by learning about all national, regional, and European funding opportunities to boost their research and innovation operations. Through information webinars, the region is bringing together private players in the blue economy and creating a common culture between different players and a group of companies.

3.11.2 Motivation for the Action

The motivation behind Occitanie's actions is twofold. First, the region aims to foster economic growth by driving innovation and creating jobs in blue economy sectors, leveraging its unique geographic location. Recognising the importance of its coastal and maritime industries, the region provides financial and operational support to businesses, ensuring they can thrive and contribute to local employment and economic resilience. Secondly, environmental sustainability is central to Occitanie's strategy. Several environmental and social challenges, including erosion of the sideline, marine submersion, marine pollution, and an ageing population and infrastructure, threaten the region, reformulating its littoral and maritime territories to meet these challenges head-on.⁴¹ By supporting innovation, Occitanie seeks to integrate sustainable practices into its economic development, protecting its natural resources while ensuring long-term resilience. The region's strategic focus on innovation aims to balance economic prosperity and environmental preservation.

⁴⁰ https://www.blued-med-initiative.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/RFW_Involvement-of-regions_Region-Occitanie_Bugeaud.pdf

⁴¹ https://www.blued-med-initiative.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/RFW_Involvement-of-regions_Region-Occitanie_Bugeaud.pdf

Another significant motivator is the network effect facilitated by the region. Occitanie creates spaces for businesses to connect, exchange expertise, and collaborate on common challenges. These networks provide access to knowledge and outside expertise and offer visibility for companies within the broader blue economy sector. Networking events organised by the region, such as meetings between the aeronautics and water sports sectors, help companies identify cross-sector synergies, find regulatory solutions, and save time navigating complex industry landscapes. This ecosystem approach, supported by both financial and operational tools, strengthens the overall competitiveness of the region's businesses and enables a more cohesive and innovative blue economy.

3.11.3 Mission Objective

Occitanie's efforts contribute to the overarching goals of Mission Ocean and Waters, particularly in promoting a sustainable blue economy and restoring marine ecosystems. The *Contrat de Filière*, by establishing strong public-private partnerships, addresses the need for economic resilience while aligning with environmental goals. Through initiatives like *Avenir Littoral*, an annual call for blue economy projects, and the *Alliance Posidonia*, the region directly supports protecting and restoring marine biodiversity. The *Label Bateau Bleu* and the Posidonia conservation initiatives also align with Mission Ocean and Waters' goals of preventing pollution and fostering carbon-neutral maritime activities. By educating businesses and providing them with the financial support to adopt greener technologies, Occitanie is driving a circular blue economy that minimises environmental harm.

3.11.4 Interaction Type

Occitanie's initiatives are based on strong collaboration between businesses, research institutions, government agencies, and NGOs. The *Contrat de Filière* was co-constructed between the region and private stakeholders, with regular consultations to ensure that it met the sector's evolving needs. This close interaction helped the region identify hidden challenges, such as customs formalities, which are barriers to sectoral growth.

Through initiatives like *Alliance Posidonia*, the region works alongside environmental NGOs and associations to promote ecological solutions. Furthermore, the region engages with companies through sectoral meetings and webinars that provide information on regional, national, and European funding opportunities. This network-building helps companies find project partners and access resources they might not be aware of.

3.11.5 Implementation

Occitanie's implementation approach is pragmatic, focused on both economic and environmental outcomes, and backed by strong political momentum. The region plays a pivotal role as a facilitator, connecting businesses with funding opportunities and providing information on innovative solutions. Through platforms such as webinars and networking events, the region presents businesses with a wide range of existing solutions and acts as a link between regional and national funding schemes. For instance, [Littoral+](#) offers companies financial contributions from the [Banque des Territoires](#), demonstrating the region's ability to connect stakeholders with both regional and national resources.

One of the region's most valuable tools is the *Avenir Littoral* fund, which finances R&D projects related to coastal protection. A successful example is the funding provided to a startup working on wave attenuators, a technology that protects coastlines from erosion. The region also supports local authorities by guiding them towards adopting these innovative solutions. Similarly, in the maritime sector, Occitanie has been instrumental in facilitating discussions between companies and

researchers, such as organising meetings to address the toxicity of antifouling products for the marine environment, ensuring that businesses can explore sustainable alternatives.

Another key factor contributing to the success of the region's initiatives is the political weight of the region, which enables it to drive maritime and economic development forward. Occitanie's regional economic development strategy allows the region to support businesses directly. The creation of the Maritime Department reflects the growing importance of maritime issues, supported by the leadership of Didier Codorniou, Vice-President of the Regional Council and President of the Parliament of the Sea. His leadership provides the momentum to push maritime issues to the forefront, aligning regional policies with both environmental and economic imperatives.

3.11.6 Outcomes

The Occitanie region's initiatives have led to significant progress in developing a sustainable blue economy, fostering innovation while addressing environmental challenges. One of the key outcomes of the region's efforts has been the successful launch of the *Avenir Littoral* fund, which led to the development of advanced solutions like wave attenuators, designed to protect coastal areas from erosion and rising sea levels, further safeguarding the region's coastline while promoting environmental resilience. The region has also achieved meaningful progress in supporting businesses through its *Contrat de Filière Nautique* initiative. This sector-specific contract, developed in consultation with over 60 companies, has successfully identified key challenges in the nautical industry and created a roadmap for sustainable growth. As a result, businesses within the sector have benefited from strategic guidance and support, enhancing their capacity to innovate while remaining environmentally sustainable. The initiative has also encouraged stronger collaboration among companies and stakeholders, facilitating the exchange of knowledge and resources.

Through projects like *Alliance Posidonia*, the region has contributed to protecting and restoring vital marine ecosystems. This initiative is particularly impactful in safeguarding Posidonia seagrass meadows, which play a crucial role in maintaining marine biodiversity and mitigating the effects of climate change by acting as carbon sinks. By preserving these habitats, Occitanie is actively working towards its environmental sustainability goals, directly contributing to protecting and restoring marine ecosystems. Moreover, the region's involvement in the *Label Bateau Bleu* project demonstrates its commitment to engaging local stakeholders and promoting eco-friendly practices in the boating industry, successfully raising awareness of sustainable boating practices, and encouraging tourists and operators to minimise their environmental impact.

Occitanie has also played a pivotal role in addressing business challenges, particularly in helping companies navigate complex regulatory and funding landscapes. The region's support through *France Expérimentation* has provided businesses with greater regulatory flexibility to test innovative projects, reducing the bureaucratic hurdles that often hinder innovation. Additionally, the region's comprehensive webinars have closed information gaps, helping businesses access national, regional, and European funding opportunities to accelerate their research and innovation activities.

3.11.7 Recommendations

3.11.7.1 For Businesses

Businesses, particularly SMEs and very small enterprises, should actively engage with regional initiatives and partnerships to leverage the tools and support available to them. The Occitanie region offers frameworks that can mitigate the risks associated with entering partnerships, including financial, legal, and technological risks. However, companies should also take advantage of dialogue opportunities with regional authorities to communicate their specific challenges and needs. Engaging

in these exchanges will help ensure that the partnerships formed are mutually beneficial and provide the desired return on investment, particularly regarding technological advancements and market opportunities.

Additionally, companies must consider the value of transparency and collaboration, even when this involves sharing innovation or entering partnerships with competitors. The support structures provided by the region, such as the competitiveness clusters (e.g., [Mediterranean Sea Cluster](#)), offer valuable opportunities for knowledge exchange and innovation, which can lead to growth in the blue economy. Embracing collaborative innovation frameworks will foster a stronger and more resilient regional blue economy sector.

3.11.7.2 For Policymakers

Policymakers should focus on reducing the administrative and regulatory burdens that discourage businesses from engaging in regional and European partnerships. The complexity of European projects, combined with the risk perception among SMEs and smaller companies, creates a barrier to participation. As such, policymakers should look to simplify these processes, making partnerships more accessible and attractive to private sector actors.

Policymakers should also continue to play the role of orchestrator, facilitating dialogue between all stakeholders in the blue economy. A specific focus should be placed on creating conditions conducive to technology transfer from research institutions to the private sector. This includes setting up tailored frameworks for technology transfer that cater to the needs of SMEs and micro-enterprises, ensuring they are involved in innovation ecosystems without risking their competitive edge or financial stability.

Moreover, there is a need to align European, national, and regional goals to better mobilise private sector participation in initiatives like S3. By promoting the benefits of participation and better communicating the return on investment to businesses, the S3 framework can be made more attractive and relevant for companies.

3.11.7.3 For Academia

Academic institutions should continue to engage with businesses and policymakers to ensure that research outcomes are efficiently transferred to the market. Universities and research centres must work proactively to reduce the knowledge gap between academia and the private sector, enabling smoother and quicker technology transfers. Research should focus on practical solutions that meet the current needs of regional industries while aligning with broader EU objectives.

In addition, academic institutions should collaborate more closely with NGOs and civil society to educate the broader community on the value of sustainable innovation in the blue economy. By fostering partnerships between research institutions, the private sector, and NGOs, academia can enhance its role in driving regional innovation and contributing to the sustainable development of the blue economy.

3.11.7.4 For NGOs and Civil Society

NGOs should be seen as essential partners in raising awareness and educating private sector players on the importance of sustainability and innovation in the blue economy. NGOs can serve as catalysts, helping to bridge gaps between research, businesses, and the public by promoting solutions that may not be immediately apparent to all stakeholders.

NGOs should also work alongside regional authorities to ensure that the least represented actors, such as SMEs and local businesses, have a voice in decision-making processes. NGOs can help create a more inclusive and cooperative regional blue economy ecosystem by facilitating dialogue between these

companies and larger entities. In this role, NGOs can be critical in supporting environmental awareness and sustainable practices, which align with regional and EU goals for marine and coastal protection.

3.12 Blekinge Region

3.12.1 Background

Blekinge is a coastal region located in Southeast Sweden that faces the Baltic Sea. Region Blekinge has integrated *Mission Ocean and Waters* and *Mission Climate Change* initiatives into its Smart Specialization Strategy (S3) to drive regional development through collaboration and innovation. The region's approach is unique as it uses both the Missions method and Smart Specialization to remove silos and emphasise cooperation among regional stakeholders, including public authorities, private businesses, research institutions, and civil society.⁴² As part of the [Kickstart S3 project \(2021-2023\)](#), the region developed a pre-study exploring innovation testbeds and their potential contribution to the blue economy and green transition. The pre-study highlighted that testbeds are essential for strengthening innovation and collaboration in areas such as marine technology, healthy oceans, and sustainable cities.⁴³ The alignment also allows the region to leverage its strengths in marine technology and innovation to address global societal challenges related to ocean sustainability and climate change. The region is working through the Marine Technology Centre of Sweden, a cluster that focuses on security, energy, and sustainable seas. This collaboration involves large companies, local universities, and various regional stakeholders to address marine and ocean sustainability issues.

Two pilots currently being led in the region exemplify Blekinge's innovation ecosystem, the first one focusing on the multi-use of marine space and the second one dedicated to the re-utilisation of microplastics. Moreover, Blekinge engages with local businesses to support them in establishing sustainability practices aligned with Mission Ocean and Waters. For instance, Blekinge has engaged with [NKT](#), a key company operating in the region that provides materials and solutions for submarine cable installations, which are critical for both the energy and defence sectors. Not only do NKT's operations contribute to the region's strategic focus on marine technology, but the company also supports environmental objectives by pursuing activities that include cleaning the seabed of debris when laying cables.

Another company that exemplifies the circular economy practices promoted by Blekinge is [Sculptur](#), a 3D printing company using recycled materials, including car bumpers, fishing nets, and forestry waste, to produce blueprints for furniture and other large-scale products. In the Kickstart S3 project pre-study, Sculptur was identified as a testbed that supports the Smart Industry specialisation of the region. By embracing additive manufacturing, Sculptur contributes to both innovation and sustainability in the blue economy while also exploring biobased and recycled material solutions. The company's process eliminates the need for custom moulds and allows material from previous print jobs to be reused, demonstrating an innovative approach to sustainable manufacturing. This innovative approach supports both environmental sustainability and local economic development by fostering new business opportunities and models and reducing plastic waste in the marine environment.

3.12.2 Motivation for the Action

Blekinge's primary motivation for integrating Mission Ocean and Waters into its strategy is to enhance sustainability and innovation within the region. Mission Ocean and Waters provides financial support and a strategic framework, facilitating mobilisation and effective collaboration across sectors of strong

⁴² <https://www.sbhss.eu/blekinge-is-on-a-mission/>

⁴³ <https://regionblekinge.se/download/18.1064653618419a9c6131dfb4/1699521284290/Blekinge%20testbed%20pre-study%20report%202022Oct%20FINAL.pdf>

relevance within the region, such as marine technology capabilities as well as industries like defence and energy. Through its Kickstart S3 pre-study, the region emphasised the importance of testbeds for validating new technologies, services, and processes in real-world conditions. These testbeds serve as collaborative spaces for companies and researchers to develop solutions addressing global challenges like pollution and climate change.⁴⁴ The Mission method has also helped this small region access critical national and European R&D programmes and investments, such as Horizon Europe, which is critical to supporting research and innovation projects in sectors like marine technology critical for the region and its economy.

3.12.3 Mission Objective

Blekinge's actions align with the Baltic-North Sea basin objective of supporting a circular and sustainable blue economy, as exemplified by its initiatives like the multi-use of ocean space involving the energy and defence sectors, as well as its support for companies like Sculptur, which promote innovative business models that, through their operations, contribute to tackling other objectives of Mission Ocean and Waters.

3.12.4 Interaction Type

Through the [Marine Technology Centre \(MTC\)](#), Blekinge Region is connected to the research community and the private sector. The MTC, also referred to as Cluster, focuses on three strategic areas: security, energy, and sustainable seas, all of which are crucially interlinked with Mission Ocean and Waters. The MTC is the primary point of contact for corporate engagement in the region, coordinating activities related to its strategic areas. Through financial support and close collaboration with the MTC, Blekinge engages with a critical sector of the business community. In the private sector, the Region primarily works with large corporate companies rather than smaller ones. Due to a lack of resources, smaller companies face higher challenges and barriers in engaging in actions linked to the Mission, partly explaining why the region has an easier time cooperating with larger companies.

The region has also identified the need for expanding testbed operations to strengthen connections between old and new testbeds, especially in marine growth areas. By connecting more established testbeds, such as the [RISE Stamping & Forming Center of Excellence](#), with new marine growth areas, the region aims to enhance the innovation ecosystem and create synergies across industries.⁴⁵ In its efforts to foster research and innovation, Blekinge also closely engages with the Blekinge Institute of Technology (BTH), a crucial regional academic partner that offers specialised programmes tailored to meet the needs of local industries, particularly in marine technology. The institution provides advanced education and research capabilities and focuses on the digitalisation of society and sustainability.

The region also engages with civil society, especially with its work on the microplastics pilot, through the "[Blekinge Archipelago](#)", a biosphere reserve organisation that promotes sustainable development across several key areas. These include fostering health and vitality in sustainable communities through sustainable mobility, strong local cycles, improved infrastructure, and increased community attractiveness. The organisation also prioritises learning and engagement for sustainable development, using research, communication, and collaboration to inspire citizens and guide them toward sustainability. Additionally, water balance and coastal protection are a central focus, with

⁴⁴ <https://regionblekinge.se/download/18.1064653618419a9c6131dfb4/1699521284290/Blekinge%20testbed%20pre-study%20report%202022Oct%20FINAL.pdf>

⁴⁵ <https://regionblekinge.se/download/18.1064653618419a9c6131dfb4/1699521284290/Blekinge%20testbed%20pre-study%20report%202022Oct%20FINAL.pdf>

efforts to maintain good water quality in streams, lakes, and oceans, ensuring a healthy coastal and archipelago environment while preserving cultural heritage. Furthermore, the Blekinge Archipelago supports biodiversity and intact ecosystem services by protecting and restoring the area's unique biodiversity and promoting sustainable use of natural resources. Lastly, the organisation encourages sustainable businesses and flourishing tourism, aiming to enhance local sustainable production and services, resource efficiency, and long-term tourism investments.⁴⁶

3.12.5 Implementation

As mentioned, the region has two leading pilots that summarise its commitment to Mission Ocean and Waters.

Multi-use Ocean Space

With the first pilot, the region seeks to combine defence and energy installations with environmental benefits, involving multiple sectors like defence, energy, fisheries, and tourism. The initiative aims to use ocean space more efficiently and sustainably, addressing geographical and strategic needs.

Microplastics

Led by the region with participation from local stakeholders, including the Marine Technology Centre and Blekinge Archipelago, this pilot has a special focus dedicated to public engagement and awareness. The project aims to reduce microplastic pollution and involves local tourism businesses, such as marinas and rental services, to engage both residents and visitors in sustainability efforts.

The region is also committed to pursuing a number of other pilot projects closely aligned with other EU Missions. During its pre-study phase, regional stakeholders affirmed their intention to leverage local strengths such as its established marine circular economy, already engaging diverse activities like mussel farming, underwater cables, and offshore wind, as well as its immigrant assimilation and foreign talent practices to support its implementation of the S3 strategy.

3.12.6 Outcomes

In carrying out its S3 strategy, Blekinge Region has successfully fostered partnerships with key stakeholders, including the defence industry, energy sector, and local universities. Collaborations with the Marine Technology Centre of Sweden and large companies such as NKT have facilitated integrated efforts to address marine and ocean sustainability issues. Moreover, the region's focus on combining defence and energy installations with environmental benefits has led to innovative multi-use ocean space initiatives.

From a public engagement perspective, the microplastics pilot project has increased public involvement in sustainability practices. The project, led by the region and involving local stakeholders like the Blekinge Archipelago, has engaged citizens and tourists in efforts to reduce microplastic pollution and involved local tourism businesses, encouraging active participation in environmental conservation.

In terms of innovation and research, joint projects with local universities, such as the Blekinge Institute of Technology (BTH), have contributed to the development of practical research applications. These collaborations have produced significant results, particularly in areas like climate adaptation and cybersecurity. BTH's participation in the climate adaptation project "Resist" and the development of

⁴⁶ <https://blekingearkipelag.se/m%C3%A5l-syfte>

digital twinning initiatives for cybersecurity affirm Blekinge's commitment to integrating research with real-world applications.

The region's engagement with companies like NKT has contributed to positive environmental outcomes, supporting large businesses in incorporating environmentally responsible practices in their operations in alignment with Mission Ocean and Waters' objectives. Through its pre-study, Blekinge identified the potential for scaling up marine and sustainability innovations by utilising testbeds as collaborative spaces for new product testing and environmental solutions. These actions also contributed to regional socio-economic development by creating new business opportunities and fostering innovation. The multi-use ocean space project, which combines defence and energy installations with environmental benefits, has the potential to attract further investments and create jobs in the region. The focus on marine technology and sustainable practices has positioned Blekinge as a leader in the blue economy, driving regional growth and development.

3.12.7 Recommendations

3.12.7.1 For Businesses

Large companies should go beyond regulatory compliance and engage in proactive sustainability initiatives. Companies in the region are increasingly focusing on sustainability, not just for compliance but to demonstrate leadership and responsibility. In the context of these efforts, businesses should look for specific impactful activities in alignment with Mission Ocean and Waters' objectives, such as NKT's efforts to clean the seabed during cable installations.

Businesses, especially SMEs and tech companies, should integrate the development of innovative technologies to solve environmental issues. For instance, Sculptur's use of recycled plastics in 3D printing furniture demonstrates how businesses can turn environmental challenges into business opportunities. Companies should also consider adopting new and innovative business models that can valorise underutilised or waste resources, much like Sculptur has done by repurposing plastic waste into valuable products. This approach not only contributes to a circular economy but also opens up new market opportunities by creating value from materials that were previously considered waste.

3.12.7.2 For Policymakers

Policymakers should continue to support applied science universities, like BTH, which play a crucial role in translating research into practical applications. The collaboration between BTH and regional initiatives like the climate adaptation project highlights the importance of such institutions.

There is a need for more streamlined and efficient regulatory processes, particularly when dealing with multi-stakeholder projects involving the defence and energy sectors. Simplifying these processes can facilitate faster project implementation and scaling.

3.12.7.3 For Academia

Universities should approach Mission Ocean and Waters innovatively, integrating research with practical applications. BTH's involvement in projects like climate adaptation and cybersecurity exemplifies this, where academic research directly supports regional development goals.

Academic institutions should continue to strengthen collaborations with industry and public sector partners. Blekinge region representatives highlight the productive partnership between BTH and local businesses, which has led to significant advancements in areas like digital twinning and cybersecurity.

4 Conclusions and Recommendations

Throughout this deliverable, we have explored the diverse ways businesses, policymakers, academia, and civil society can align their actions with the ambitious goals of Mission Ocean and Waters. The case studies presented offer insights into successful strategies for fostering innovation, driving sustainable economic growth, and protecting marine ecosystems. From cutting-edge aquaculture solutions to cross-border collaborations, each initiative illustrates how different sectors can contribute to building a carbon-neutral, circular, and resilient blue economy. Drawing from these case studies, we have identified several key recommendations for various stakeholders involved in the sustainable blue economy.

4.1 For Businesses

Invest in Partnerships and Collaboration:

- Businesses should consider establishing partnerships with research institutions, universities, and other companies to support them in driving innovation and developing their sustainable solutions.

Leverage Funding Opportunities:

- SMEs in the blue economy should tap into programmes such as BlueInvest, SBEP, and EIT KICs to access funding for developing market-ready sustainable solutions. However, businesses need to be aware of the administrative complexities and the need for long-term commitment.

Focus on Market Readiness and Business Models:

- It is crucial to align innovations with the market's needs and the objectives of broader environmental frameworks. For instance, DEME's nature-based projects illustrate how companies can integrate long-term environmental benefits into their business strategies while considering market realities.

Adopt Sustainable Technologies:

- Aligning business models with market needs while incorporating sustainable technologies will not only enhance profitability but also contribute significantly to achieving Mission Ocean and Waters' objectives. Businesses can take inspiration from Kongsberg's efforts to reduce emissions and improve operational efficiency through energy-efficient technologies.

4.2 For Policymakers

Simplify Funding and Regulatory Processes:

- Streamline the lengthy and complex funding and permitting processes for sustainable blue economy projects. This recommendation comes from insights provided by DEME and NextTuna, where regulatory delays significantly hindered project timelines.

Promote Place-Based Innovation:

- Support place-based innovation by fostering cooperation between regional authorities and businesses, as seen in the EIT KICs as well as in regional success stories like Blekinge. Ensuring that regional strategies (e.g., S3/S4) are aligned with innovation objectives helps to stimulate local economies and meet global sustainability goals.

Provide Incentives for Sustainability:

- Policymakers should incentivise businesses to adopt circular economy principles and sustainable technologies. This includes financial incentives, tax breaks, and easing access to public contracts, as emphasised by BlueInvest and SBEP.

4.3 For Academia

Enhance Knowledge Transfer:

- Universities and research institutions should prioritise applied research and knowledge transfer to businesses. Blekinge particularly emphasised the key role that applied universities play in fostering regional innovation, while KIC WMM, EIT Food, and SBEP underlined the importance of academic innovations having clear business and market value.

Create Programmes Aligned with Industry Needs:

- Educational programmes should be aligned with the skill needs of the blue economy sectors. Kongsberg's collaboration with the University of South-Eastern Norway for industry-based master's programmes is an excellent model.

4.4 For NGOs and Civil Society

Promote Community Engagement:

- NGOs should focus on raising awareness and engaging local communities in sustainability efforts. GeoStud's NGO, Natura 5, shows how translating scientific information into accessible language can help mobilise and engage local stakeholders in conservation initiatives.

Support Policy and Advocacy Efforts:

- NGOs should continue to advocate for more robust policies that align with Mission Ocean and Waters' objectives, also in alignment with projects and initiatives carried forward by companies, particularly in the areas of pollution reduction and biodiversity restoration, as emphasised in projects like DEME's Reefcovery initiative.

5 ANNEXES

5.1 Interview Questionnaire

The PREP4BLUE project and Task 5.5

Background and goal - Mission Ocean

Inspired by the Apollo 11 mission, the Horizon Europe (HE) Missions seek to enable large-scale transformations as solutions to some of the greatest challenges facing our world (fighting cancer, climate change, protecting our oceans, living in greener cities and ensuring soil health and food). The Missions' approach intends to link initiatives across different disciplines, mobilise policymakers, stakeholders and citizens, and leverage public and private investments towards their goals. Within this framework, the objective of the Mission Ocean and Waters is to restore the health of our ocean, seas and waters by 2030, with three measurable, specific goals: 1) to protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, 2) to prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters and 3) to make the Blue Economy sustainable, carbon neutral and circular.

The Mission will be implemented in two different phases: a first "development and piloting" phase (2021-2025), followed by a second "deployment and upscaling" phase (2026-2030). During the first phase, specific lighthouse (LH) areas will each pilot one specific Mission's measurable goal, as shown in the figure below.

Background and goal - the PREP4BLUE project

The PREP4BLUE project (2022-2026) functions as an EU-wide Coordination and Support Action for the Mission Ocean. The goal of the project is to develop the R&I implementation modalities required to achieve the Mission objectives and to facilitate a successful first phase (2022-2025). In terms of CSA impact, the role is to support the LH initiatives at all project lifecycle stages (design, implementation, completion, scale up) and ultimately help ensure that the generated knowledge/solutions can move down their respective impact pathways.

One of the important aspects influencing those pathways towards further valorisation, is regulation and policy. Innovative solutions and new developments, such as those that will be researched, piloted and upscaled within the Lighthouse areas, are not always in a 1-to-1 agreement with prevailing policies and regulations: think of alternative activities in wind farms, but also, for example, fast track permitting for marine research. Policy and regulations can, therefore, be a support, but also a potential obstacle.

Background and goal - this interview

Within task 5.5 of the PREP4BLUE project, we are investigating best-case study examples of approaches for interaction with the business community to ensure effective rollout and long-term financing of the objectives of Mission Ocean. **Your contribution will help broaden our insight into the “on the ground” experiences with innovative solutions and approaches that have succeeded in bolstering private sector participation** in the financing of Mission-aligned initiatives. These examples may not have occurred formally under Mission Ocean, but they are still valuable representations of financially sustainable efforts toward its objectives. Your insights will also contribute to providing input towards the way forward, in the form of solutions and good practices that we can learn from you.

Your participation

You were selected to participate in this study because of your professional expertise and background. The partners and their contact networks chose a selection of stakeholders best suited for this interview setting in terms of experience and interest. Your willingness to share your expertise and experiences as such is of utmost importance for the project's output and will support other stakeholders in working towards Mission Ocean's objectives.

Practicalities

The foreseen interviews will be conducted between June and August 2024 by at least one representative of s.Pro, or by one representative from one of the contributing partners (ERINN, CPMR, IFREMER and JPIO). The interviews will take place online on MS Teams and last approximately between 45min and 1h15. To ensure a sound analysis of the interviews and a correct interpretation of the answers, the conversation will be recorded to allow transcription and coding. **Therefore, the interviewee is asked to sign a consent form before the interview.** The interview recordings WILL NOT be shared publicly.

GDPR and personal data collected in the project

We will not collect personal information about you directly in this project; however, we will collect it indirectly. First, we will have recordings of your consent to participate and tape recordings of the interview for quality purposes. We will delete the latter when the interview is transcribed. Your consent will be deleted at the end of the project period (February 2025).

We will only use your information for the purposes described in this letter. All information from the study will be treated with confidentiality, and the data will be anonymised by the end of the project or deleted. You will never be identified when results are published. Personal data will be processed according to the requirements of data protection legislation (GDPR).

Interview Questions

1. Can you share a specific example of a successful business model or initiative (involving an interaction with the business community or, if you are from the business community, with the public or research sector) that supported the Mission Ocean objectives? What was your role in this initiative?
 - **Possible examples of Business models:** *circular economy model, renewable energy and environmental restoration, sustainable fisheries and aquaculture, blue carbon projects, marine pollution solutions, eco-friendly shipping, CSR initiatives.*
2. What were the main challenges you or others encountered while implementing this initiative? How were these challenges addressed and overcome?
3. **For Businesses:** What was the primary motive or the 'business case' that motivated you to initiate/join the project/activity?
For Others: What was the primary motive or the 'business case' that motivated the business/company to join your project/initiative?
4. What key factors contributed to the success of this initiative?
 - *Examples could include internal factors (e.g., company policies, leadership) and/or external factors (e.g., regulatory environment, partnerships).*
5. How were other stakeholders (e.g., citizens and local communities, government agencies, NGOs, academia, media) engaged in the initiative? Did you enact specific strategies to engage one or more stakeholder groups?
For the public sector: How did your policy or initiative engage stakeholders from the business community?
6. What elements of this model or initiative do you believe are crucial for its replication in other regions or contexts?
 - *Can you think of any specific conditions that need to be met to ensure the success of similar initiatives?*
7. What were the most significant lessons learned from this initiative? How can these lessons inform future initiatives or business models that support, directly or indirectly, Mission Ocean's objectives?
8. Based on this experience, what recommendations would you give to any of the following groups looking to support similar initiatives in support of Mission Ocean objectives?
 - a. *Businesses (looking to engage in such initiatives)*
 - b. *Academic institutions*
 - c. *Policymakers*
 - d. *NGOs and community groups*
 - Are there any best practices or strategies you would highlight?

Written consent

I have received and understood information about the PREP4BLUE project, and I have been given the opportunity to ask questions. I consent to:

- Participate in the interview and answer the questions;
- My personal data (recordings of interviews) are stored after the session until transcribed or by the end of the project period at the latest.

I consent to all my personal data being treated until the conclusion of the PREP4BLUE project.

(Signed by participant, date and place)